

Tectonics

Supporting Information for

Provenance of the Mesozoic succession of Franz Josef Land (north-eastern Barents Sea): Paleogeographic and tectonic implications for the High Arctic

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Attachment 5 Results of U-Pb dating of detrital zircons from Mesozoic clastics of FJL.

sample 7-v15-9	coordinates		80°25.563'				059°39.570'											
								207/235		206/238		207/206		Best age				
Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	Age Ma	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	(Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*		
7-v15-9_100.FIN2	207.3	1.185	0.2376	0.009	0.03325	0.00081	0.47276	215.9	7.3	210.8	5.1	269	71	210.8	5.1	2		
7-v15-9_28.FIN2	93.1	0.717	0.2422	0.0086	0.03432	0.0007	0.049451	219.6	7	217.5	4.4	254	85	217.5	4.4	1		
7-v15-9_25.FIN2	85	1.084	0.259	0.013	0.0345	0.0011	0.009834	232	11	218.4	6.9	370	120	218.4	6.9	6		
7-v15-9_18.FIN2	175.5	1.007	0.2537	0.0059	0.03556	0.00063	0.14671	229.1	4.8	225.2	3.9	263	54	225.2	3.9	2		
7-v15-9_125.FIN2	141	0.765	0.262	0.012	0.03606	0.00063	0.44274	235.8	9.4	228.3	3.9	276	85	228.3	3.9	3		
7-v15-9_30.FIN2	143.6	0.793	0.2523	0.0075	0.03614	0.0007	0.32632	227.8	6.1	228.8	4.4	220	65	228.8	4.4	0		
7-v15-9_88.FIN2	249	1.006	0.2605	0.0072	0.03658	0.00082	0.44903	234.5	5.8	231.5	5.1	267	59	231.5	5.1	1		
7-v15-9_43.FIN2	196	1.119	0.272	0.0089	0.03777	0.00092	0.41942	243.6	7	238.9	5.7	285	67	238.9	5.7	2		
7-v15-9_12.FIN2	87.6	0.539	0.277	0.01	0.03811	0.00074	0.32608	247.1	8.3	241	4.6	290	73	241	4.6	2		
7-v15-9_82.FIN2	300.9	1.072	0.2759	0.0084	0.0382	0.001	0.44108	247.1	6.7	241.9	6.4	280	71	241.9	6.4	2		
7-v15-9_123.FIN2	253	0.615	0.2832	0.0088	0.03908	0.00095	0.43656	252.5	7	247.1	5.9	304	66	247.1	5.9	2		
7-v15-9_86.FIN2	148.7	1.118	0.2771	0.0086	0.03954	0.00099	0.46271	247.6	6.8	249.9	6.1	226	61	249.9	6.1	1		
7-v15-9_6.FIN2	74.9	1.17	0.2901	0.0091	0.03971	0.00081	0.20324	258.9	7.4	251	5	318	74	251	5	3		
7-v15-9_16.FIN2	56.2	4.11	0.299	0.016	0.0398	0.00078	0.22204	263	13	251.5	4.9	340	110	251.5	4.9	4		
7-v15-9_108.FIN2	66.4	0.809	0.303	0.011	0.04003	0.00075	0.12743	267.3	8.6	252.9	4.7	376	81	252.9	4.7	5		
7-v15-9_89.FIN2	238	0.803	0.2914	0.0064	0.0408	0.00069	0.3416	259.2	5	257.7	4.3	269	48	257.7	4.3	1		
7-v15-9_80.FIN2	120	0.443	0.2956	0.0097	0.0409	0.00097	0.58009	262	7.5	258.3	6	288	62	258.3	6	1		
7-v15-9_44.FIN2	83.6	0.823	0.321	0.014	0.0411	0.001	0.22416	281	10	259.4	6.3	448	91	259.4	6.3	8		
7-v15-9_124.FIN2	80.8	0.815	0.339	0.015	0.0458	0.0014	0.36862	297	11	288.4	8.8	357	87	288.4	8.8	3		
7-v15-9_14.FIN2	316.6	1.236	0.3402	0.0072	0.04622	0.00095	0.51977	296.9	5.5	291.2	5.8	339	48	291.2	5.8	2		
7-v15-9_47.FIN2	301	0.8153	0.3406	0.008	0.04637	0.00067	0.43098	297.2	6.1	292.2	4.1	329	48	292.2	4.1	2		
7-v15-9_5.FIN2	277.9	1.356	0.3551	0.0073	0.04701	0.00085	0.52773	308.1	5.5	296.1	5.2	375	44	296.1	5.2	4		
7-v15-9_20.FIN2	218	1.094	0.3609	0.0092	0.04968	0.00083	0.55368	312.1	6.9	312.5	5.1	289	47	312.5	5.1	0		
7-v15-9_85.FIN2	35.43	0.915	0.367	0.021	0.0501	0.0016	0.1942	318	16	314.8	9.7	330	120	314.8	9.7	1		
7-v15-9_101.FIN2	80.7	0.674	0.377	0.013	0.0503	0.0011	0.23154	323.5	9.5	316.1	6.8	366	77	316.1	6.8	2		
7-v15-9_57.FIN2	265.3	1.313	0.3611	0.0097	0.0504	0.0012	0.49485	312.2	7.2	316.8	7.3	272	55	316.8	7.3	1		
7-v15-9_114.FIN2	125	1.066	0.3802	0.0093	0.05083	0.0009	0.092786	326.5	6.9	319.6	5.5	386	64	319.6	5.5	2		
7-v15-9_117.FIN2	261	0.762	0.3947	0.0097	0.05128	0.00095	0.43067	337.1	7.1	322.3	5.9	415	53	322.3	5.9	4		
7-v15-9_99.FIN2	376	0.802	0.381	0.013	0.0517	0.002	0.57447	326.3	9.5	325	12	363	71	325	12	0		
7-v15-9_119.FIN2	102.2	0.774	0.384	0.01	0.05281	0.00084	0.37209	329.2	7.6	331.7	5.2	306	57	331.7	5.2	1		
7-v15-9_113.FIN2	272	1.048	0.399	0.011	0.0537	0.0013	0.49344	341.4	8.2	337.2	7.8	370	58	337.2	7.8	1		
7-v15-9_22.FIN2	156	0.883	0.404	0.011	0.0538	0.0011	0.3173	343.6	8.3	337.5	7	373	63	337.5	7	2		
7-v15-9_96.FIN2	376	2.19	0.3978	0.0094	0.0539	0.0013	0.52441	339.2	6.8	338.5	8	353	52	338.5	8	0		
7-v15-9_29.FIN2	71.6	1.148	0.402	0.014	0.0545	0.0013	0.40839	342	10	342.2	7.8	341	76	342.2	7.8	0		
7-v15-9_115.FIN2	67.3	0.758	0.41	0.013	0.05485	0.00094	0.2037	347.6	9.6	344.1	5.7	356	70	344.1	5.7	1		
7-v15-9_126.FIN2	268	1.024	0.461	0.019	0.0554	0.0011	0.42475	382	13	347.6	6.5	569	77	347.6	6.5	9		
7-v15-9_92.FIN2	176.3	1.922	0.4165	0.0098	0.05547	0.00098	0.47439	352.7	7	347.9	6	359	48	347.9	6	1		
7-v15-9_116.FIN2	408	1.08	0.416	0.0067	0.05562	0.00079	0.41255	352.8	4.8	348.9	4.8	375	38	348.9	4.8	1		
7-v15-9_61.FIN2	124.4	1.341	0.4183	0.0088	0.0557	0.001	0.36094	354.1	6.3	349.2	6.2	398	51	349.2	6.2	1		
7-v15-9_53.FIN2	202	1.007	0.4224	0.0096	0.05672	0.00069	0.34891	356.9	6.9	355.6	4.2	347	48	355.6	4.2	0		
7-v15-9_74.FIN2	60.9	0.828	0.432	0.014	0.05799	0.0009	0.24307	363	10	363.3	5.5	354	70	363.3	5.5	0		

7-v15-9_46.FIN2	61.1	0.6	0.46	0.017	0.0601	0.0012	0.27235	383	12	376	7.4	424	81	376	7.4	2
7-v15-9_23.FIN2	170.7	0.895	0.4605	0.0098	0.0602	0.0011	0.17081	383.8	6.8	376.7	6.5	418	55	376.7	6.5	2
7-v15-9_51.FIN2	112.1	0.4155	0.461	0.012	0.0604	0.001	0.24435	384	8	379	6.3	408	57	379	6.3	1
7-v15-9_121.FIN2	177.7	66.1	0.495	0.036	0.0623	0.004	0.87374	402	24	389	24	484	81	389	24	3
7-v15-9_105.FIN2	199.1	3.28	0.476	0.017	0.0625	0.0021	0.69095	394	11	391	13	417	58	391	13	1
7-v15-9_68.FIN2	102.2	0.622	0.487	0.012	0.06288	0.00097	0.27208	401.9	8.4	393	5.9	438	57	393	5.9	2
7-v15-9_84.FIN2	115.5	1.762	0.497	0.018	0.0648	0.0021	0.54675	409	12	404	13	418	71	404	13	1
7-v15-9_4.FIN2	111.9	0.811	0.517	0.013	0.067	0.0012	0.40521	421.9	8.8	417.9	7.5	427	55	417.9	7.5	1
7-v15-9_122.FIN2	333.1	59	0.524	0.01	0.0674	0.0013	0.43177	427.4	6.9	420.4	7.6	460	46	420.4	7.6	2
7-v15-9_48.FIN2	120.6	1.764	0.554	0.017	0.0679	0.0018	0.36344	447	11	423	11	564	68	423	11	5
7-v15-9_8.FIN2	270	1.643	0.522	0.01	0.068	0.0013	0.33183	427	6.5	424.1	8.1	413	49	424.1	8.1	1
7-v15-9_10.FIN2	143	0.984	0.523	0.014	0.0682	0.0013	0.60285	425.6	9.1	424.9	7.7	409	46	424.9	7.7	0
7-v15-9_41.FIN2	522	1.046	0.539	0.013	0.0682	0.0015	0.42096	437.2	8.5	425.2	9.3	499	55	425.2	9.3	3
7-v15-9_109.FIN2	213.3	0.698	0.533	0.011	0.0694	0.0012	0.44527	433.1	6.9	432.2	7.3	430	43	432.2	7.3	0
7-v15-9_69.FIN2	101.9	1.204	0.529	0.022	0.0696	0.0027	0.44208	429	14	433	16	400	91	433	16	1
7-v15-9_26.FIN2	108.1	2.08	0.544	0.015	0.0697	0.0014	0.40796	439.7	9.9	434.2	8.5	459	59	434.2	8.5	1
7-v15-9_128.FIN2	80	0.42	0.574	0.023	0.0697	0.0013	0.23456	457	14	434.4	7.8	597	90	434.4	7.8	5
7-v15-9_118.FIN2	64	0.423	0.554	0.016	0.0706	0.00098	0.28358	446	11	439.7	5.9	454	63	439.7	5.9	1
7-v15-9_45.FIN2	363	8.2	0.556	0.011	0.0711	0.0014	0.36457	447.7	7.3	442.6	8.2	463	47	442.6	8.2	1
7-v15-9_63.FIN2	123.7	0.938	0.545	0.015	0.0711	0.0012	0.49133	440.6	9.9	442.7	7.3	421	54	442.7	7.3	0
7-v15-9_33.FIN2	6.41	1.34	0.523	0.049	0.0713	0.0026	0.07457	416	34	443	16	270	180	443	16	6
7-v15-9_72.FIN2	273	0.723	0.57	0.014	0.0723	0.0017	0.47244	457	9.2	450	10	475	53	450	10	2
7-v15-9_103.FIN2	527	1.019	0.632	0.02	0.0726	0.0021	0.46167	496	12	451	12	686	70	451	12	9
7-v15-9_3.FIN2	266	0.611	0.559	0.012	0.073	0.0012	0.53022	449.9	7.6	454.3	7	420	40	454.3	7	1
7-v15-9_21.FIN2	248	0.799	0.583	0.011	0.0739	0.0011	0.5198	465.2	6.9	459.5	6.4	496	35	459.5	6.4	1
7-v15-9_37.FIN2	170	1.502	0.583	0.014	0.074	0.0016	0.4667	465.3	8.7	459.9	9.4	467	51	459.9	9.4	1
7-v15-9_42.FIN2	61.1	1.029	0.632	0.021	0.0741	0.0018	0.30032	497	14	461	11	650	77	461	11	7
7-v15-9_78.FIN2	78.5	0.96	0.598	0.017	0.0751	0.0014	0.2941	474	11	466.9	8.5	500	61	466.9	8.5	1
7-v15-9_32.FIN2	142	2.36	0.618	0.026	0.0774	0.0036	0.33514	486	16	480	21	510	100	480	21	1
7-v15-9_87.FIN2	244.9	1.201	0.684	0.013	0.0802	0.0012	0.42712	527.9	8	497.3	7.4	655	41	497.3	7.4	6
7-v15-9_127.FIN2	39.6	0.655	0.715	0.028	0.0835	0.0019	0.44821	544	17	517	11	658	80	517	11	5
7-v15-9_56.FIN2	109	0.845	0.68	0.015	0.0851	0.0012	0.33113	525.5	8.8	526.4	7.3	521	45	526.4	7.3	0
7-v15-9_79.FIN2	35.5	1.27	0.693	0.023	0.0865	0.0018	0.31302	533	14	535	10	499	72	535	10	0
7-v15-9_15.FIN2	87.4	1.227	0.711	0.021	0.0877	0.0018	0.29496	544	13	542	11	541	66	542	11	0
7-v15-9_7.FIN2	48.9	0.781	0.777	0.022	0.0909	0.0017	0.18683	582	13	562.2	9.7	647	71	562.2	9.7	3
7-v15-9_71.FIN2	145	2.12	0.766	0.017	0.0929	0.0015	0.44634	575.6	9.7	572.3	8.9	580	43	572.3	8.9	1
7-v15-9_19.FIN2	398	0.695	0.848	0.017	0.1007	0.002	0.68466	622.3	9.2	618	12	626	35	618	12	1
7-v15-9_120.FIN2	28.4	0.276	0.838	0.036	0.1017	0.002	0.37305	614	20	624	12	550	85	624	12	2
7-v15-9_39.FIN2	119.3	1.603	0.918	0.018	0.1066	0.0017	0.44491	659.7	9.7	652.6	9.6	674	40	652.6	9.6	1
7-v15-9_75.FIN2	351	0.951	0.939	0.02	0.1107	0.0022	0.69668	672	11	676	13	643	39	676	13	1
7-v15-9_34.FIN2	18.6	1.895	0.978	0.039	0.1123	0.0028	0.20718	688	21	686	16	657	94	686	16	0
7-v15-9_83.FIN2	167.9	0.412	0.977	0.022	0.1139	0.0025	0.50962	690	11	695	15	674	47	695	15	1
7-v15-9_110.FIN2	376.3	36.5	1.01	0.016	0.115	0.0016	0.59483	708	7.9	701.5	9.1	728	28	701.5	9.1	1
7-v15-9_81.FIN2	45.5	1.101	1.135	0.045	0.1253	0.0038	0.40676	767	22	760	22	772	85	760	22	1
7-v15-9_65.FIN2	100	1.363	1.198	0.025	0.1317	0.0031	0.57061	801	11	796	18	801	45	796	18	1

7-v15-9_50.FIN2	27.1	0.241	1.256	0.055	0.1357	0.0043	0.36842	824	25	819	24	825	90	819	24	1	
7-v15-9_107.FIN2	185	0.833	1.28	0.028	0.1379	0.0031	0.5096	835	12	832	17	846	43	832	17	0	
7-v15-9_130.FIN2	56.8	1.002	1.311	0.036	0.1409	0.0027	0.1902	848	16	849	15	835	64	849	15	0	
7-v15-9_31.FIN2	286	0.904	1.395	0.033	0.146	0.0035	0.64768	885	14	878	20	912	42	878	20	1	
7-v15-9_58.FIN2	133.4	1.745	1.355	0.033	0.1481	0.0039	0.52657	867	14	889	22	817	51	889	22	3	
7-v15-9_54.FIN2	188	5.18	1.452	0.03	0.1526	0.0029	0.77053	910	12	915	17	900	33	915	17	1	
7-v15-9_52.FIN2	97.4	0.885	1.669	0.024	0.1684	0.002	0.39616	995.2	9.3	1003	11	977	31	977	11	1	
7-v15-9_112.FIN2	170	4.81	1.666	0.066	0.165	0.0066	0.56286	990	25	983	37	1013	76	983	37	1	
7-v15-9_24.FIN2	422	10.5	1.777	0.043	0.1748	0.0039	0.64077	1037	15	1037	22	1017	41	1017	41	2	
7-v15-9_55.FIN2	171	2.03	1.751	0.069	0.1711	0.0043	0.84912	1020	24	1020	24	1018	40	1018	40	0	
7-v15-9_17.FIN2	78.6	1.205	1.789	0.032	0.1722	0.0024	0.49169	1040	12	1024	13	1074	32	1074	32	5	
7-v15-9_73.FIN2	356	2.522	2.964	0.067	0.2442	0.0049	0.68517	1400	16	1407	25	1381	34	1381	34	2	
7-v15-9_66.FIN2	48.7	1.394	3.355	0.07	0.2662	0.0056	0.53778	1490	17	1519	28	1457	38	1457	38	4	
7-v15-9_27.FIN2	174	5.23	3.97	0.1	0.3028	0.0088	0.47333	1626	21	1702	43	1523	50	1523	50	12	
7-v15-9_97.FIN2	20.7	0.674	4.345	0.094	0.2986	0.005	0.37023	1699	18	1683	24	1711	41	1711	41	2	
7-v15-9_36.FIN2	156.6	0.648	4.04	0.15	0.2768	0.0089	0.78254	1633	31	1580	47	1716	42	1716	42	8	
7-v15-9_98.FIN2	104.5	2.005	4.701	0.093	0.3183	0.0057	0.73372	1763	16	1780	28	1747	25	1747	25	2	
7-v15-9_11.FIN2	130	1.277	4.631	0.066	0.3115	0.0039	0.43477	1752	12	1750	20	1755	23	1755	23	0	
7-v15-9_2.FIN2	315.9	0.908	5.135	0.051	0.3323	0.003	0.52766	1840.9	8.6	1851	14	1828	16	1828	16	1	
7-v15-9_106.FIN2	353	15.96	5.325	0.08	0.3456	0.005	0.6541	1873	13	1912	24	1828	24	1828	24	5	
7-v15-9_77.FIN2	84.1	1.158	5.47	0.086	0.3528	0.0041	0.50529	1895	14	1947	19	1834	27	1834	27	6	
7-v15-9_91.FIN2	94	0.96	5.27	0.15	0.326	0.011	0.63126	1864	24	1812	53	1914	50	1914	50	5	
7-v15-9_70.FIN2	73.3	0.399	6.69	0.14	0.3833	0.0091	0.60552	2067	19	2088	42	2035	36	2035	36	3	
7-v15-9_40.FIN2	6.63	0.998	6.42	0.18	0.3512	0.0088	0.24871	2025	26	1936	42	2109	62	2109	62	8	
7-v15-9_49.FIN2	31.35	0.485	7.86	0.23	0.398	0.011	0.62112	2207	27	2155	52	2254	41	2254	41	4	
7-v15-9_93.FIN2	200.4	1.381	8.97	0.29	0.4387	0.008	0.79924	2321	32	2342	36	2302	40	2302	40	2	
7-v15-9_102.FIN2	75.1	0.574	9.09	0.12	0.4245	0.0063	0.57839	2345	12	2283	28	2397	22	2397	22	5	
7-v15-9_64.FIN2	13.88	1.106	10.49	0.33	0.4676	0.0092	0.55808	2472	29	2471	41	2467	45	2467	45	0	
7-v15-9_62.FIN2	140	0.33	11	0.18	0.4958	0.0091	0.63232	2523	14	2593	39	2470	24	2470	24	5	
7-v15-9_76.FIN2	50.8	0.746	10.55	0.24	0.467	0.011	0.75066	2480	20	2470	49	2487	27	2487	27	1	
7-v15-9_90.FIN2	321.4	1.657	11.83	0.29	0.482	0.013	0.68281	2585	23	2527	59	2624	33	2624	33	4	
7-v15-9_95.FIN2	68.3	1.101	13.25	0.27	0.521	0.012	0.59433	2693	20	2709	52	2684	38	2684	38	1	
7-v15-9_104.FIN2	251	2.7	15.11	0.25	0.558	0.013	0.53326	2818	16	2849	55	2814	36	2814	36	1	
7-v15-9_35.FIN2	45.8	2.25	19.8	1.1	0.614	0.023	0.92107	3014	67	3063	94	2996	57	2996	57	2	
sample 11-v15-1	coordinates	80°24.695'															
		059°42.964'															
								207/235		206/238		207/206		Best age			
Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	Age Ma	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	(Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*	
11_v15_1_31.FIN2	775	1.227	0.2357	0.0049	0.03153	0.00059	0.54187	214.7	4	200.1	3.7	361	38	200.1	3.7	7	
11_v15_1_104.FIN2	550	0.845	0.237	0.0055	0.03175	0.00063	0.21638	215.7	4.5	201.5	4	351	49	201.5	4	7	
11_v15_1_106.FIN2	229	0.499	0.2534	0.0095	0.03262	0.00079	0.56778	228.5	7.7	206.8	4.9	420	67	206.8	4.9	9	
11_v15_1_123.FIN2	133.2	0.513	0.2464	0.0089	0.03406	0.00087	0.13008	223	7.2	215.8	5.4	288	74	215.8	5.4	3	
11_v15_1_90.FIN2	166	0.988	0.2629	0.0078	0.03426	0.00049	0.15095	236.5	6.2	217.1	3	416	67	217.1	3	8	
11_v15_1_30.FIN2	255	0.714	0.2624	0.0082	0.03647	0.00077	0.31968	236.1	6.6	230.8	4.8	283	54	230.8	4.8	2	
11_v15_1_20.FIN2	490	1.089	0.2742	0.0055	0.03856	0.00049	0.31171	245.8	4.4	243.9	3.1	260	45	243.9	3.1	1	

11_v15_1_71.FIN2	243	1.76	0.2794	0.0054	0.03907	0.00038	0.23771	249.8	4.3	247	2.4	268	43	247	2.4	1
11_v15_1_91.FIN2	126.9	0.799	0.313	0.011	0.0394	0.00099	0.44875	275.8	8.6	249.1	6.1	496	71	249.1	6.1	10
11_v15_1_5.FIN2	241.7	0.364	0.2849	0.0059	0.03966	0.0005	0.17143	254.2	4.6	250.7	3.1	254	47	250.7	3.1	1
11_v15_1_105.FIN2	240.2	1.65	0.2847	0.0055	0.0398	0.00051	0.14063	254.1	4.3	251.6	3.1	269	47	251.6	3.1	1
11_v15_1_15.FIN2	97	0.744	0.291	0.01	0.04067	0.00059	0.23313	259.7	8.3	257	3.6	266	73	257	3.6	1
11_v15_1_82.FIN2	477	1.28	0.307	0.01	0.041	0.0011	0.77652	271.3	7.8	259.1	6.7	374	47	259.1	6.7	4
11_v15_1_125.FIN2	255	1.423	0.3276	0.0091	0.0411	0.0011	0.50139	288.2	7.2	259.6	7	524	60	259.6	7	10
11_v15_1_114.FIN2	147.5	1.012	0.3	0.011	0.0418	0.001	0.52157	266.4	8.6	263.7	6.4	270	65	263.7	6.4	1
11_v15_1_26.FIN2	360	0.984	0.3048	0.0066	0.04246	0.00074	0.54096	269.8	5.2	268	4.6	272	47	268	4.6	1
11_v15_1_8.FIN2	234.2	0.4062	0.3076	0.0068	0.04265	0.00045	0.18803	272	5.3	269.2	2.8	294	53	269.2	2.8	1
11_v15_1_74.FIN2	282	1.125	0.3114	0.0083	0.0427	0.00046	0.5116	274.9	6.4	269.5	2.9	309	51	269.5	2.9	2
11_v15_1_87.FIN2	307	1.158	0.3281	0.0066	0.04483	0.00075	0.59659	287.7	5	282.7	4.6	332	38	282.7	4.6	2
11_v15_1_47.FIN2	91.6	0.987	0.342	0.012	0.04592	0.00064	0.13529	298.2	8.9	289.4	4	345	75	289.4	4	3
11_v15_1_10.FIN2	331	0.97	0.341	0.0069	0.04596	0.00061	0.28182	297.6	5.2	289.7	3.7	357	47	289.7	3.7	3
11_v15_1_41.FIN2	224.1	0.814	0.3407	0.0071	0.04671	0.00067	0.34046	297.3	5.3	294.3	4.1	309	47	294.3	4.1	1
11_v15_1_85.FIN2	181.9	0.906	0.3553	0.0069	0.0471	0.00056	0.19159	308.4	5.2	296.7	3.4	392	46	296.7	3.4	4
11_v15_1_103.FIN2	157.8	1.71	0.364	0.01	0.0476	0.001	0.48128	314.2	7.4	299.7	6.3	407	58	299.7	6.3	5
11_v15_1_108.FIN2	181.2	0.777	0.3487	0.0079	0.04771	0.00055	0.47632	303.3	5.9	300.4	3.4	320	46	300.4	3.4	1
11_v15_1_61.FIN2	303	0.743	0.3513	0.0059	0.04807	0.00054	0.34924	305.3	4.4	302.6	3.3	316	37	302.6	3.3	1
11_v15_1_16.FIN2	137.1	0.703	0.3699	0.0092	0.04876	0.00069	0.15345	318.8	6.8	306.8	4.2	382	58	306.8	4.2	4
11_v15_1_124.FIN2	61.3	0.996	0.398	0.016	0.04877	0.00074	0.17884	338	11	306.9	4.5	526	85	306.9	4.5	9
11_v15_1_98.FIN2	299	1.675	0.359	0.016	0.0493	0.0022	0.6374	310	12	310	13	348	72	310	13	0
11_v15_1_83.FIN2	459.2	1.103	0.3823	0.006	0.05033	0.00046	0.088668	328.6	4.4	316.5	2.8	403	37	316.5	2.8	4
11_v15_1_59.FIN2	792	2.18	0.407	0.014	0.0516	0.0017	0.83214	345.2	9.7	324	10	489	41	324	10	6
11_v15_1_119.FIN2	145.4	3.13	0.4144	0.0098	0.05214	0.00055	0.048573	351.4	7	327.6	3.3	488	56	327.6	3.3	7
11_v15_1_22.FIN2	171.8	1.792	0.428	0.01	0.0523	0.0012	0.33935	361.2	7.2	328.3	7.4	582	56	328.3	7.4	9
11_v15_1_111.FIN2	151.8	1.4	0.389	0.012	0.0525	0.0016	0.5111	332.2	8.7	329	10	392	66	329	10	1
11_v15_1_28.FIN2	260.6	1.3	0.3983	0.0085	0.05338	0.00092	0.45887	340.5	6.3	335.1	5.6	371	47	335.1	5.6	2
11_v15_1_116.FIN2	227	0.797	0.4322	0.0087	0.05562	0.00069	0.2873	364.3	6.2	348.9	4.2	454	46	348.9	4.2	4
11_v15_1_19.FIN2	39.1	1.363	0.421	0.019	0.0557	0.0016	0.48802	354	13	349	10	339	84	349	10	1
11_v15_1_112.FIN2	198	1.237	0.451	0.013	0.0579	0.0011	0.5007	377.5	9.1	362.6	6.8	459	57	362.6	6.8	4
11_v15_1_44.FIN2	488	0.568	0.4728	0.008	0.05808	0.00098	0.79381	392.7	5.5	363.8	6	562	27	363.8	6	7
11_v15_1_38.FIN2	427	1.889	0.4418	0.009	0.0594	0.0012	0.65597	370.8	6.4	371.8	7	364	39	371.8	7	0
11_v15_1_92.FIN2	345	0.664	0.473	0.012	0.0595	0.0013	0.56229	392.7	8.2	372.4	8.1	511	50	372.4	8.1	5
11_v15_1_62.FIN2	47.5	0.987	0.461	0.016	0.06024	0.00093	0.15447	385	11	377	5.6	422	77	377	5.6	2
11_v15_1_60.FIN2	242.8	0.64	0.4582	0.0085	0.06026	0.00086	0.46385	382.4	5.9	377.2	5.2	397	38	377.2	5.2	1
11_v15_1_48.FIN2	372	0.805	0.478	0.013	0.0612	0.0011	0.67733	396.1	8.9	382.9	6.5	447	43	382.9	6.5	3
11_v15_1_34.FIN2	629.1	21.1	0.4831	0.0077	0.06262	0.00062	0.46398	400	5.3	391.5	3.8	431	30	391.5	3.8	2
11_v15_1_14.FIN2	307	0.839	0.5038	0.0086	0.0627	0.001	0.51981	413.9	5.8	391.9	6.1	533	34	391.9	6.1	5
11_v15_1_89.FIN2	245.2	1.095	0.5016	0.0099	0.06327	0.00099	0.46583	412.2	6.7	395.4	6	508	42	395.4	6	4
11_v15_1_75.FIN2	168.7	0.756	0.478	0.011	0.0634	0.0012	0.51203	395.9	7.4	395.9	7.1	385	47	395.9	7.1	0
11_v15_1_100.FIN2	121.1	1.298	0.513	0.013	0.064	0.0011	0.53908	419.9	9	400	6.9	532	52	400	6.9	5
11_v15_1_130.FIN2	56.9	1.416	0.499	0.015	0.0646	0.0012	0.29284	410	10	403.3	7.1	434	66	403.3	7.1	2
11_v15_1_11.FIN2	108.5	0.4698	0.542	0.014	0.06573	0.00076	0.11761	438.5	9.4	410.4	4.6	569	59	410.4	4.6	6
11_v15_1_81.FIN2	234.7	0.382	0.565	0.014	0.06597	0.00086	0.54913	453.8	8.8	411.7	5.2	669	45	411.7	5.2	9

11_v15_1_122.FIN2	194.1	1.159	0.546	0.015	0.0699	0.0012	0.1351	441.9	9.5	435.7	7.5	465	63	435.7	7.5	1
11_v15_1_65.FIN2	79.5	0.913	0.564	0.018	0.071	0.002	0.49447	452	11	442	12	489	65	442	12	2
11_v15_1_12.FIN2	378	1.718	0.5418	0.009	0.07108	0.00089	0.52029	439.1	5.9	442.6	5.4	413	33	442.6	5.4	1
11_v15_1_13.FIN2	174.7	1.162	0.5549	0.0092	0.07137	0.00077	0.24542	447.6	6	444.4	4.6	445	39	444.4	4.6	1
11_v15_1_49.FIN2	204.9	1.978	0.571	0.015	0.0719	0.0016	0.25293	457.8	9.4	447.3	9.8	503	64	447.3	9.8	2
11_v15_1_128.FIN2	346	3.272	0.5564	0.0086	0.07193	0.00072	0.31241	448.8	5.6	447.8	4.3	449	35	447.8	4.3	0
11_v15_1_109.FIN2	173.9	0.797	0.595	0.012	0.076	0.0011	0.46696	473.1	7.9	471.9	6.8	466	42	471.9	6.8	0
11_v15_1_93.FIN2	97.9	0.323	0.59	0.015	0.0762	0.0018	0.43108	469.7	9.9	473	11	423	59	473	11	1
11_v15_1_9.FIN2	116.3	0.892	0.601	0.013	0.07696	0.00086	0.22681	476.8	8.1	477.9	5.1	456	48	477.9	5.1	0
11_v15_1_63.FIN2	86.5	1.03	0.615	0.017	0.0775	0.0011	0.26667	486	11	481.1	6.8	491	60	481.1	6.8	1
11_v15_1_25.FIN2	63.5	0.2878	0.632	0.021	0.0786	0.0016	0.33009	496	13	487.4	9.4	516	71	487.4	9.4	2
11_v15_1_43.FIN2	109.3	0.921	0.676	0.017	0.0787	0.0014	0.3416	525	11	489.1	8.6	668	56	489.1	8.6	7
11_v15_1_45.FIN2	141	0.85	0.666	0.016	0.0789	0.0013	0.38297	516.5	9.8	490.4	8	619	52	490.4	8	5
11_v15_1_55.FIN2	99.5	1.08	0.693	0.018	0.0824	0.0014	0.42143	535	11	510.6	8.3	633	54	510.6	8.3	5
11_v15_1_36.FIN2	225.3	0.917	0.69	0.016	0.0844	0.0017	0.71309	531.6	9.6	522	10	571	38	522	10	2
11_v15_1_23.FIN2	64.6	0.863	0.774	0.022	0.0846	0.0013	0.072779	580	13	523.3	7.5	790	66	523.3	7.5	10
11_v15_1_120.FIN2	159.2	0.546	0.82	0.016	0.0989	0.002	0.44794	608.2	8.6	608	12	615	44	608	12	0
11_v15_1_129.FIN2	249.4	1.358	0.853	0.018	0.1005	0.0016	0.54365	625	10	617.4	9.2	649	41	617.4	9.2	1
11_v15_1_32.FIN2	136.8	0.58	1.066	0.016	0.1186	0.0011	0.15518	736.4	8.1	722.4	6.5	769	36	722.4	6.5	2
11_v15_1_1.FIN2	179	1.74	1.12	0.026	0.1239	0.0023	0.67442	764	12	753	14	775	40	753	14	1
11_v15_1_80.FIN2	21.62	0.3831	1.144	0.046	0.1242	0.0028	0.3424	771	21	754	16	808	79	754	16	2
11_v15_1_96.FIN2	195	1.188	1.323	0.037	0.1289	0.0034	0.78567	853	16	781	19	1049	35	781	19	8
11_v15_1_94.FIN2	82.8	1.457	1.24	0.034	0.1364	0.0032	0.42043	819	16	824	18	801	58	824	18	1
11_v15_1_72.FIN2	386	3.03	1.436	0.033	0.1392	0.0024	0.69701	902	14	840	13	1066	33	840	13	7
11_v15_1_113.FIN2	61.71	1.193	1.363	0.034	0.1411	0.0025	0.35166	871	15	851	14	925	50	851	14	2
11_v15_1_40.FIN2	217	1.042	1.395	0.028	0.142	0.0023	0.70358	887	11	856	13	958	29	856	13	3
11_v15_1_6.FIN2	221.6	1.094	1.323	0.017	0.1443	0.0014	0.27209	855.3	7.3	869	7.7	809	27	869	7.7	2
11_v15_1_76.FIN2	7.27	1.025	1.573	0.086	0.1553	0.0037	0.07466	952	33	930	21	970	120	930	21	2
11_v15_1_4.FIN2	351	0.929	1.658	0.031	0.1611	0.0029	0.95693	990	12	962	16	1047	17	962	16	3
11_v15_1_121.FIN2	71.1	1.17	1.689	0.034	0.1673	0.0029	0.51209	1001	13	997	16	1013	39	997	16	0
11_v15_1_7.FIN2	169.8	1.629	1.929	0.031	0.1844	0.0032	0.40345	1090	11	1090	17	1090	39	1090	39	0
11_v15_1_95.FIN2	41.9	0.934	1.851	0.038	0.1751	0.003	0.30743	1064	14	1040	17	1111	46	1111	46	6
11_v15_1_68.FIN2	128.3	1.303	2.024	0.027	0.187	0.0021	0.37538	1122.4	9.2	1105	11	1165	27	1165	27	5
11_v15_1_33.FIN2	79.6	1.122	2.125	0.053	0.189	0.0041	0.57922	1153	17	1115	22	1220	42	1220	42	9
11_v15_1_126.FIN2	171	1.271	2.145	0.029	0.1897	0.0023	0.49485	1162.7	9.3	1119	12	1237	26	1237	26	10
11_v15_1_101.FIN2	111	1.76	2.243	0.063	0.1886	0.0052	0.48726	1190	20	1112	28	1331	46	1331	46	16
11_v15_1_118.FIN2	111.6	0.5569	2.776	0.047	0.2312	0.0037	0.60472	1347	13	1340	19	1357	29	1357	29	1
11_v15_1_66.FIN2	232	2.04	2.253	0.03	0.1875	0.0023	0.78601	1197.1	9.3	1107	12	1364	24	1364	24	19
11_v15_1_57.FIN2	274	0.4249	3.379	0.056	0.2632	0.0039	0.69094	1498	13	1506	20	1482	22	1482	22	2
11_v15_1_39.FIN2	227	1.248	3.097	0.058	0.2303	0.0048	0.79162	1431	14	1334	25	1577	27	1577	27	15
11_v15_1_102.FIN2	38.7	0.961	3.163	0.074	0.2342	0.0048	0.45861	1450	18	1355	25	1578	44	1578	44	14
11_v15_1_51.FIN2	125	0.873	3.963	0.062	0.2931	0.0052	0.53715	1625	13	1656	26	1579	30	1579	30	5
11_v15_1_17.FIN2	102.4	0.736	3.961	0.063	0.2905	0.0046	0.74332	1626	14	1643	23	1601	27	1601	27	3
11_v15_1_35.FIN2	602	1.268	3.54	0.051	0.2575	0.0042	0.73278	1534	12	1476	22	1612	19	1612	19	8
11_v15_1_88.FIN2	49.2	1.146	3.798	0.098	0.271	0.0062	0.74022	1586	21	1544	31	1656	34	1656	34	7

11_v15_1_78.FIN2	48.4	0.787	4.19	0.083	0.2948	0.0054	0.65876	1668	16	1664	27	1672	28	1672	28	0	
11_v15_1_56.FIN2	53.8	0.39	5.74	0.098	0.3638	0.0067	0.53746	1935	15	1998	32	1862	32	1862	32	7	
11_v15_1_18.FIN2	93.6	0.849	6.264	0.099	0.36	0.0044	0.63532	2011	14	1981	21	2047	22	2047	22	3	
11_v15_1_50.FIN2	291	5.45	8.51	0.15	0.4248	0.0087	0.473	2285	16	2278	39	2297	35	2297	35	1	
11_v15_1_67.FIN2	85.5	0.907	13.58	0.16	0.5288	0.0062	0.59044	2719	11	2735	26	2705	18	2705	18	1	
11_v15_1_2.FIN2	85.5	0.542	14.29	0.14	0.5463	0.0059	0.66923	2768.9	9.3	2808	25	2735	14	2735	14	3	
sample 15AP25	coordinates	80°25'27.8"															
		59°39'58.2"															
								207/235		206/238		207/206			Best age		
Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	Age Ma	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	(Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*	
15AP25_38.FIN2	39.5	1.438	0.298	0.015	0.04259	0.00091	0.17761	264	12	268.8	5.6	215	95	268.8	5.6	2	
15AP25_113.FIN2	217	0.413	0.3159	0.0088	0.04382	0.00096	0.55343	279.8	7.1	276.4	5.9	305	54	276.4	5.9	1	
15AP25_15.FIN2	98.5	0.4322	0.3158	0.0097	0.04403	0.00057	0.28055	278	7.5	277.7	3.5	272	64	277.7	3.5	0	
15AP25_92.FIN2	25.52	0.652	0.324	0.017	0.04443	0.00098	0.13173	282	13	280.1	6	290	100	280.1	6	1	
15AP25_69.FIN2	395	6.09	0.326	0.0059	0.04473	0.0006	0.19533	286.2	4.5	282.1	3.7	308	41	282.1	3.7	1	
15AP25_6.FIN2	27.2	0.579	0.332	0.02	0.0453	0.0012	0.089104	289	15	285.2	7.1	300	120	285.2	7.1	1	
15AP25_125.FIN2	57.1	0.948	0.324	0.013	0.0455	0.0012	0.28751	283.9	9.9	286.8	7.1	278	86	286.8	7.1	1	
15AP25_106.FIN2	61.4	0.754	0.352	0.019	0.0457	0.0015	0.30412	304	14	287.8	9.3	410	100	287.8	9.3	5	
15AP25_112.FIN2	74.9	0.767	0.33	0.014	0.0464	0.0011	0.5036	290	11	292.2	6.5	255	79	292.2	6.5	1	
15AP25_46.FIN2	91.8	1.07	0.351	0.013	0.04657	0.0008	0.2313	304	10	293.4	4.9	358	81	293.4	4.9	3	
15AP25_31.FIN2	27.8	1.042	0.374	0.022	0.0472	0.0013	0.11782	319	16	297	7.7	450	130	297	7.7	7	
15AP25_32.FIN2	334	2.08	0.3697	0.0098	0.04718	0.00095	0.033339	318.5	7.2	297.1	5.8	460	56	297.1	5.8	7	
15AP25_26.FIN2	113.5	0.827	0.3454	0.0096	0.04738	0.00089	0.30091	300.6	7.2	298.3	5.5	317	62	298.3	5.5	1	
15AP25_91.FIN2	51.27	0.645	0.358	0.027	0.0482	0.0011	0.27868	309	20	303.6	6.6	330	150	303.6	6.6	2	
15AP25_5.FIN2	350	1.228	0.3561	0.0065	0.04873	0.00063	0.38239	309	4.8	306.7	3.9	318	39	306.7	3.9	1	
15AP25_10.FIN2	89.1	0.959	0.364	0.011	0.04937	0.00094	0.11806	314.4	8.2	310.5	5.8	329	71	310.5	5.8	1	
15AP25_66.FIN2	62.8	0.783	0.36	0.012	0.04944	0.00065	0.062526	310.7	8.8	311	4	303	71	311	4	0	
15AP25_40.FIN2	119.7	0.907	0.374	0.011	0.05016	0.00067	0.311	323.1	7.9	315.5	4.1	358	63	315.5	4.1	2	
15AP25_89.FIN2	125.9	0.844	0.375	0.013	0.0506	0.0014	0.3618	322.2	9.4	318.1	8.7	368	75	318.1	8.7	1	
15AP25_121.FIN2	319	0.745	0.41	0.012	0.0515	0.0013	0.55292	348.2	8.7	323.6	7.8	512	59	323.6	7.8	7	
15AP25_96.FIN2	46.9	1.003	0.382	0.014	0.05147	0.00085	0.14789	327	11	324.2	5.4	331	81	324.2	5.4	1	
15AP25_44.FIN2	135.8	0.888	0.401	0.012	0.0516	0.0013	0.46141	341.1	8.3	324.4	8.1	445	62	324.4	8.1	5	
15AP25_94.FIN2	91	0.765	0.392	0.014	0.0519	0.0014	0.17115	334	10	325.9	8.8	388	88	325.9	8.8	2	
15AP25_124.FIN2	31.5	1.117	0.402	0.018	0.0522	0.0014	0.16488	342	14	328.1	8.8	413	97	328.1	8.8	4	
15AP25_85.FIN2	69.1	1.437	0.388	0.017	0.0523	0.0014	0.49488	330	12	328.5	8.5	308	78	328.5	8.5	0	
15AP25_77.FIN2	96.9	0.486	0.389	0.012	0.0525	0.0011	0.43795	332.4	8.7	329.7	6.7	345	62	329.7	6.7	1	
15AP25_33.FIN2	572	0.792	0.3844	0.0049	0.05301	0.00058	0.25758	330.6	3.7	333	3.6	313	34	333	3.6	1	
15AP25_25.FIN2	74.9	1.098	0.407	0.012	0.0533	0.0011	0.19947	346.6	9.2	334.9	6.6	414	72	334.9	6.6	3	
15AP25_111.FIN2	144.1	1.479	0.404	0.016	0.0537	0.0017	0.45365	344	11	337	10	395	77	337	10	2	
15AP25_82.FIN2	70.2	0.471	0.398	0.011	0.05392	0.00092	0.15406	340.5	8.4	338.5	5.6	354	69	338.5	5.6	1	
15AP25_45.FIN2	64.5	1.086	0.406	0.014	0.0541	0.0011	0.23346	346	10	339.5	6.4	363	75	339.5	6.4	2	
15AP25_61.FIN2	107.8	1.146	0.423	0.011	0.05451	0.00086	0.42888	358.4	8.3	342.1	5.2	442	57	342.1	5.2	5	
15AP25_65.FIN2	86.9	0.891	0.401	0.012	0.05453	0.00079	0.15128	341.1	8.8	342.2	4.8	322	67	342.2	4.8	0	
15AP25_114.FIN2	95.9	0.945	0.413	0.026	0.0549	0.0028	0.62784	346	18	344	17	357	90	344	17	1	
15AP25_4.FIN2	57.2	0.6004	0.418	0.014	0.0558	0.0012	0.14975	353	10	349.7	7.3	368	78	349.7	7.3	1	

15AP25_37.FIN2	90	1.088	0.424	0.013	0.0568	0.0011	0.17225	357.1	9.4	356.1	6.6	353	70	356.1	6.6	0
15AP25_2.FIN2	282.2	1.95	0.426	0.0082	0.05703	0.00092	0.2323	360.5	6	357.4	5.6	367	50	357.4	5.6	1
15AP25_78.FIN2	24.5	2.15	0.427	0.026	0.0575	0.0019	0.32972	357	18	360	11	360	120	360	11	1
15AP25_22.FIN2	90.7	0.98	0.432	0.012	0.05772	0.00089	0.1283	365	8.4	361.7	5.4	375	63	361.7	5.4	1
15AP25_3.FIN2	43.1	1.464	0.463	0.017	0.0582	0.0011	0.1977	386	12	364.7	7	483	79	364.7	7	6
15AP25_7.FIN2	43	1.232	0.442	0.018	0.0582	0.0011	0.21836	370	13	364.7	6.6	380	85	364.7	6.6	1
15AP25_63.FIN2	445	4.33	0.4385	0.0063	0.05838	0.00064	0.43725	368.8	4.4	365.8	3.9	387	31	365.8	3.9	1
15AP25_84.FIN2	178	1.116	0.439	0.011	0.0587	0.0011	0.23244	368.8	7.8	367.9	6.9	366	55	367.9	6.9	0
15AP25_107.FIN2	98.4	0.959	0.448	0.017	0.0593	0.0017	0.53218	374	12	371	10	399	75	371	10	1
15AP25_51.FIN2	143	1.236	0.462	0.011	0.06086	0.00086	0.18845	384.9	7.6	380.8	5.2	391	56	380.8	5.2	1
15AP25_60.FIN2	80.3	1.535	0.46	0.015	0.0612	0.0013	0.2945	383	10	383	7.8	368	68	383	7.8	0
15AP25_30.FIN2	39.4	2.011	0.464	0.015	0.06129	0.00085	0.15119	385	10	383.4	5.1	388	72	383.4	5.1	0
15AP25_71.FIN2	296	0.781	0.4635	0.0097	0.0616	0.0012	0.5219	385.9	6.7	385.3	7.3	391	44	385.3	7.3	0
15AP25_54.FIN2	131	1.69	0.474	0.011	0.0617	0.00092	0.23537	392.8	7.7	385.9	5.6	416	50	385.9	5.6	2
15AP25_64.FIN2	74.8	1.087	0.481	0.016	0.0631	0.0015	0.4728	397	11	394.4	9.1	411	64	394.4	9.1	1
15AP25_50.FIN2	120.2	0.941	0.506	0.016	0.0634	0.0015	0.49757	415	10	396.3	9.1	493	64	396.3	9.1	5
15AP25_122.FIN2	40.7	1.027	0.498	0.02	0.0636	0.0012	0.059912	408	14	397.3	7.3	443	83	397.3	7.3	3
15AP25_36.FIN2	37.9	2.478	0.467	0.02	0.0638	0.0013	0.1713	387	14	398.9	7.7	305	90	398.9	7.7	3
15AP25_28.FIN2	197	0.816	0.512	0.013	0.0675	0.0011	0.37168	418.8	8.7	420.7	6.6	396	56	420.7	6.6	0
15AP25_100.FIN2	47.6	1.198	0.517	0.027	0.0682	0.0029	0.39054	419	18	425	17	410	100	425	17	1
15AP25_93.FIN2	86.8	0.736	0.517	0.017	0.0684	0.0016	0.24555	423	11	426.1	9.7	398	73	426.1	9.7	1
15AP25_80.FIN2	304	1.126	0.523	0.0099	0.06868	0.00089	0.29868	426.4	6.6	428.1	5.3	407	44	428.1	5.3	0
15AP25_49.FIN2	55.7	0.749	0.52	0.02	0.0688	0.0018	0.24551	423	14	429	11	364	87	429	11	1
15AP25_119.FIN2	71.4	0.511	0.528	0.019	0.0696	0.0023	0.44141	428	13	433	14	409	77	433	14	1
15AP25_75.FIN2	242	0.67	0.544	0.01	0.06987	0.00085	0.42676	440.1	6.7	435.3	5.1	456	39	435.3	5.1	1
15AP25_19.FIN2	529	0.57	0.536	0.011	0.07	0.0015	0.48619	436.1	7.7	435.8	9.1	444	51	435.8	9.1	0
15AP25_110.FIN2	194	1.479	0.562	0.012	0.072	0.0011	0.3206	452.1	7.7	448.2	6.8	462	48	448.2	6.8	1
15AP25_35.FIN2	75.2	0.5196	0.595	0.018	0.0723	0.0014	0.058378	473	12	449.8	8.2	571	78	449.8	8.2	5
15AP25_16.FIN2	97.1	1.411	0.584	0.017	0.0723	0.0015	0.24279	466	11	450.1	9.1	546	68	450.1	9.1	3
15AP25_1.FIN2	161.5	0.73	0.562	0.011	0.073	0.001	0.4376	452.9	7.6	453.8	6	447	43	453.8	6	0
15AP25_118.FIN2	133	0.754	0.569	0.012	0.0732	0.001	0.38021	456.4	7.9	455.8	6.3	455	46	455.8	6.3	0
15AP25_57.FIN2	66.6	0.5891	0.562	0.016	0.0738	0.00089	0.084551	451	10	459	5.3	404	63	459	5.3	2
15AP25_129.FIN2	242	0.985	0.579	0.015	0.0748	0.0022	0.55124	463.6	9.9	465	13	459	53	465	13	0
15AP25_83.FIN2	221.4	0.957	0.605	0.015	0.0774	0.002	0.47904	482.9	9.6	481	12	492	60	481	12	0
15AP25_130.FIN2	275	0.949	0.623	0.014	0.0784	0.0017	0.48564	490.5	8.5	486	10	510	48	486	10	1
15AP25_68.FIN2	86	0.542	0.639	0.015	0.0817	0.0011	0.16865	500.6	9.3	505.9	6.8	475	57	505.9	6.8	1
15AP25_126.FIN2	93.4	1.537	0.69	0.021	0.0863	0.0022	0.55745	530	12	533	13	515	62	533	13	1
15AP25_74.FIN2	46.2	3.74	0.7	0.031	0.0869	0.0024	0.33985	533	18	537	14	516	90	537	14	1
15AP25_116.FIN2	99.5	0.98	0.733	0.036	0.0893	0.0037	0.60366	551	20	550	22	549	87	550	22	0
15AP25_52.FIN2	186	2.841	0.722	0.013	0.0906	0.0013	0.25937	550.9	7.7	558.8	7.8	513	44	558.8	7.8	1
15AP25_9.FIN2	13	0.3971	0.737	0.035	0.0908	0.0018	0.007654	554	21	560	11	500	110	560	11	1
15AP25_41.FIN2	44.6	0.788	0.743	0.022	0.0928	0.0016	0.16432	562	13	572.2	9.2	506	70	572.2	9.2	2
15AP25_117.FIN2	52.96	0.758	0.792	0.022	0.098	0.0019	0.42459	590	13	602	11	548	59	602	11	2
15AP25_70.FIN2	597	4.25	0.8189	0.0076	0.09967	0.00082	0.41456	607.7	4.3	612.4	4.8	584	19	612.4	4.8	1
15AP25_24.FIN2	243.2	1.441	0.893	0.014	0.1056	0.0015	0.31907	646.8	7.6	646.9	9	641	31	646.9	9	0

Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	207/235 Age Ma	2σ error	206/238 Age (Ma)	2σ error	207/206 Age (Ma)	2σ error	Best age (Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*
13_V15_1_36.FIN2	183.7	0.813	0.2408	0.0068	0.03124	0.00053	0.25739	218.7	5.6	198.3	3.3	328	65	198.3	3.3	9.327846365
13_V15_1_118.FIN2	97.3	0.519	0.2603	0.0096	0.03473	0.00068	0.043584	234.3	7.7	220	4.2	372	85	220	4.2	6.103286385
13_V15_1_26.FIN2	122.7	0.611	0.2466	0.0096	0.0354	0.0011	0.30793	223.7	8	224	6.9	222	83	224	6.9	0.134108181
13_V15_1_21.FIN2	222.3	0.867	0.2502	0.0061	0.03537	0.00054	0.33236	226.9	4.8	224.5	3.2	231	52	224.5	3.2	1.057734685
13_V15_1_65.FIN2	286	0.891	0.2497	0.0068	0.03566	0.00055	0.46073	225.9	5.5	225.9	3.4	230	52	225.9	3.4	0
13_V15_1_105.FIN2	187.9	0.583	0.2654	0.0077	0.03698	0.00056	0.16817	238.7	6.2	234.1	3.5	271	66	234.1	3.5	1.927105153
13_V15_1_64.FIN2	345	0.3361	0.2834	0.0067	0.03813	0.00076	0.5145	253.8	5.5	241.2	4.7	354	47	241.2	4.7	4.964539007
13_V15_1_84.FIN2	429	0.5881	0.2981	0.0065	0.03851	0.00074	0.57822	264.5	5	243.5	4.6	451	42	243.5	4.6	7.939508507
13_V15_1_53.FIN2	433.7	0.83	0.2769	0.0066	0.03852	0.00085	0.3574	247.9	5.2	243.6	5.3	292	59	243.6	5.3	1.734570391
13_V15_1_104.FIN2	313	0.941	0.2844	0.0078	0.03945	0.00092	0.52724	253.5	6.1	249.3	5.7	290	54	249.3	5.7	1.656804734
13_V15_1_112.FIN2	103.6	0.748	0.2822	0.0084	0.0401	0.00067	0.26378	251.6	6.6	253.4	4.2	236	63	253.4	4.2	0.715421304
13_V15_1_92.FIN2	397	0.687	0.2945	0.0054	0.0409	0.00056	0.2942	261.9	4.2	258.4	3.5	299	43	258.4	3.5	1.336387934
13_V15_1_116.FIN2	504	1.139	0.3101	0.0066	0.04224	0.00079	0.43332	274	5.1	266.7	4.9	334	47	266.7	4.9	2.664233577
13_V15_1_34.FIN2	409	0.51	0.3236	0.0053	0.04455	0.00058	0.45803	284.4	4.1	280.9	3.6	301	37	280.9	3.6	1.230661041
13_V15_1_106.FIN2	176	0.875	0.3165	0.008	0.04459	0.00076	0.36911	278.5	6.2	281.1	4.7	262	54	281.1	4.7	0.933572711
13_V15_1_50.FIN2	571	1.767	0.3439	0.0084	0.0453	0.0014	0.63116	300.3	6.2	285.6	8.5	417	58	285.6	8.5	4.895104895
13_V15_1_71.FIN2	197	0.589	0.3308	0.007	0.04551	0.0007	0.37325	291.1	5.6	286.8	4.3	316	46	286.8	4.3	1.477155617
13_V15_1_70.FIN2	222	0.838	0.3639	0.0091	0.04729	0.00088	0.23091	314.7	6.8	297.8	5.4	424	60	297.8	5.4	5.370193835
13_V15_1_123.FIN2	185.2	1.287	0.3613	0.008	0.04745	0.0008	0.29067	312.7	6	298.8	4.9	404	53	298.8	4.9	4.445155101
13_V15_1_103.FIN2	122.6	0.52	0.3482	0.0079	0.04809	0.00071	0.25292	302.7	6	302.7	4.3	297	53	302.7	4.3	0
13_V15_1_93.FIN2	433	18.54	0.376	0.01	0.0495	0.0012	0.59135	323.6	7.6	311.5	7.1	401	47	311.5	7.1	3.739184178
13_V15_1_33.FIN2	172	1.13	0.3739	0.0092	0.04967	0.00072	0.40565	322.8	7	312.4	4.4	376	51	312.4	4.4	3.22180917
13_V15_1_58.FIN2	505	1.134	0.375	0.01	0.05	0.001	0.41677	323.1	7.6	314.6	6.3	377	58	314.6	6.3	2.630764469
13_V15_1_39.FIN2	50.25	1.116	0.371	0.014	0.0504	0.001	0.26759	321	11	317.2	6.3	334	80	317.2	6.3	1.183800623
13_V15_1_91.FIN2	257	1.137	0.3696	0.0071	0.05057	0.00076	0.36576	318.8	5.2	318	4.6	312	43	318	4.6	0.250941029
13_V15_1_61.FIN2	346	1.61	0.3989	0.0063	0.05073	0.00074	0.3547	340.6	4.6	319	4.5	474	39	319	4.5	6.341749853
13_V15_1_122.FIN2	279.8	0.914	0.406	0.0089	0.05106	0.00078	0.37539	345.5	6.4	321	4.8	511	46	321	4.8	7.091172214
13_V15_1_95.FIN2	120	0.905	0.3983	0.0092	0.05344	0.00073	0.075041	339.8	6.7	335.5	4.5	358	57	335.5	4.5	1.265450265
13_V15_1_38.FIN2	119	0.902	0.405	0.011	0.05393	0.00099	0.35961	345.2	8	338.5	6	379	59	338.5	6	1.940903824
13_V15_1_115.FIN2	74.5	0.908	0.426	0.012	0.055	0.0012	0.33994	359.6	8.3	344.9	7.2	456	64	344.9	7.2	4.087875417
13_V15_1_124.FIN2	112.7	0.869	0.405	0.021	0.055	0.0022	0.68987	343	15	345	13	335	94	345	13	0.583090379
13_V15_1_16.FIN2	135	0.793	0.43	0.018	0.0554	0.0024	0.44015	361	13	347	15	470	95	347	15	3.878116343
13_V15_1_20.FIN2	55.9	1.031	0.406	0.014	0.0554	0.0016	0.41065	344	10	347.3	9.6	323	77	347.3	9.6	0.959302326
13_V15_1_51.FIN2	145.8	1.75	0.435	0.015	0.0555	0.0017	0.5181	365	11	348	10	474	65	348	10	4.657534247
13_V15_1_101.FIN2	88.1	0.94	0.411	0.014	0.0556	0.0015	0.53746	347.6	9.9	348.8	9.2	342	66	348.8	9.2	0.345224396
13_V15_1_85.FIN2	198	0.658	0.431	0.014	0.05767	0.00093	0.3057	364	10	361.4	5.7	350	71	361.4	5.7	0.714285714
13_V15_1_14.FIN2	145.6	0.341	0.46	0.013	0.05893	0.00073	0.21721	382.8	8.6	369.1	4.5	442	59	369.1	4.5	3.578892372
13_V15_1_127.FIN2	427	1.6	0.433	0.012	0.0591	0.0015	0.3734	365	8.6	370.2	9.2	338	68	370.2	9.2	1.424657534
13_V15_1_129.FIN2	168	1.047	0.441	0.011	0.0591	0.0011	0.46556	370.8	7.6	370.2	6.7	363	53	370.2	6.7	0.161812298
13_V15_1_15.FIN2	351	0.669	0.443	0.0073	0.05954	0.0009	0.45356	371.9	5.1	372.7	5.5	370	33	372.7	5.5	0.215111589
13_V15_1_31.FIN2	244	0.831	0.4552	0.0094	0.0604	0.0011	0.43367	380.1	6.5	377.7	6.7	384	47	377.7	6.7	0.631412786
13_V15_1_18.FIN2	282.4	2.34	0.4542	0.0092	0.061	0.0011	0.61105	379.7	6.4	381.5	6.6	360	37	381.5	6.6	0.474058467
13_V15_1_89.FIN2	197	1.138	0.462	0.01	0.0617	0.001	0.32809	384.9	7.3	386.4	6.3	371	49	386.4	6.3	0.389711613

13_V15_1_86.FIN2	74	1.31	0.472	0.02	0.0626	0.0024	0.46882	390	13	393	15	399	86	393	15	0.769230769
13_V15_1_35.FIN2	480	1.8	0.525	0.022	0.0642	0.0027	0.91875	426	14	401	16	580	35	401	16	5.868544601
13_V15_1_17.FIN2	166.4	1.311	0.531	0.014	0.0649	0.0016	0.42405	431.4	9.5	405.4	9.8	575	59	405.4	9.8	6.026889198
13_V15_1_87.FIN2	111.8	0.617	0.497	0.017	0.065	0.0018	0.60975	408	12	406	11	402	69	406	11	0.490196078
13_V15_1_54.FIN2	83.1	1.392	0.506	0.017	0.0654	0.0016	0.52614	414	11	407.9	9.6	429	70	407.9	9.6	1.473429952
13_V15_1_72.FIN2	64.2	0.485	0.524	0.014	0.0662	0.0011	0.35711	426	9.7	413.1	6.9	476	60	413.1	6.9	3.028169014
13_V15_1_128.FIN2	31.88	1.43	0.577	0.035	0.0673	0.0022	0.44107	457	22	420	14	600	120	420	14	8.096280088
13_V15_1_6.FIN2	43.48	1.49	0.531	0.017	0.0677	0.0013	0.33673	430	12	422.2	7.8	446	69	422.2	7.8	1.813953488
13_V15_1_55.FIN2	368	7.9	0.532	0.0068	0.06947	0.00077	0.32463	432.7	4.5	433.5	4.8	431	32	433.5	4.8	0.184885602
13_V15_1_8.FIN2	124.4	2.59	0.552	0.017	0.0699	0.0017	0.42135	447	11	435	10	488	67	435	10	2.684563758
13_V15_1_42.FIN2	176.1	0.702	0.56	0.012	0.0708	0.0014	0.48231	451	8	440.8	8.7	508	48	440.8	8.7	2.261640798
13_V15_1_47.FIN2	139.3	0.578	0.621	0.022	0.0709	0.0012	0.27937	490	14	441.3	7.1	696	70	441.3	7.1	9.93877551
13_V15_1_76.FIN2	161.6	0.707	0.56	0.011	0.07166	0.00081	0.14037	451.2	6.9	446.1	4.9	470	46	446.1	4.9	1.130319149
13_V15_1_90.FIN2	201	14	0.562	0.014	0.0719	0.0012	0.40403	451.7	8.8	447.3	7.2	461	50	447.3	7.2	0.974097853
13_V15_1_2.FIN2	193.4	0.755	0.566	0.013	0.072	0.0015	0.43009	454.3	8.2	448.3	9.2	470	50	448.3	9.2	1.320713185
13_V15_1_46.FIN2	103.8	0.587	0.557	0.017	0.0723	0.0021	0.44305	449	12	449	12	446	63	449	12	0
13_V15_1_25.FIN2	223.8	0.836	0.594	0.011	0.073	0.0012	0.38741	475.8	7.7	454.2	7.2	573	44	454.2	7.2	4.539722573
13_V15_1_52.FIN2	208.9	1.56	0.622	0.016	0.0733	0.0014	0.53008	490	10	455.8	8.6	645	50	455.8	8.6	6.979591837
13_V15_1_56.FIN2	220.6	0.952	0.634	0.02	0.0745	0.0025	0.65668	498	12	463	15	663	56	463	15	7.02811245
13_V15_1_110.FIN2	206.6	0.696	0.594	0.015	0.0757	0.0016	0.53019	472.5	9.2	470.1	9.4	494	50	470.1	9.4	0.507936508
13_V15_1_67.FIN2	352	2.391	0.616	0.0081	0.07692	0.00076	0.53759	486.9	5.1	477.7	4.5	526	27	477.7	4.5	1.889505032
13_V15_1_130.FIN2	363.6	9.2	0.6299	0.0097	0.07823	0.00094	0.4172	495.7	6	485.5	5.6	528	32	485.5	5.6	2.057696187
13_V15_1_22.FIN2	94.6	1.38	0.663	0.018	0.081	0.0016	0.44977	514	11	501.6	9.6	555	54	501.6	9.6	2.412451362
13_V15_1_30.FIN2	145.8	0.916	0.68	0.016	0.0822	0.0014	0.33243	525.9	9.5	508.9	8.5	585	52	508.9	8.5	3.232553717
13_V15_1_99.FIN2	211	0.633	0.654	0.013	0.0823	0.0012	0.47212	510.3	7.9	509.7	7.4	534	37	509.7	7.4	0.117577895
13_V15_1_102.FIN2	471	2.161	0.679	0.01	0.0842	0.0011	0.64186	525.9	6.1	521	6.3	563	26	521	6.3	0.931736071
13_V15_1_11.FIN2	162.2	64	0.698	0.048	0.0849	0.0066	0.60782	534	29	524	39	580	140	524	39	1.872659176
13_V15_1_126.FIN2	228	0.835	0.737	0.017	0.0865	0.0014	0.51332	559.4	9.8	534.4	8.4	667	42	534.4	8.4	4.469074008
13_V15_1_37.FIN2	174	0.497	0.733	0.021	0.0877	0.0023	0.71271	557	12	542	14	607	57	542	14	2.692998205
13_V15_1_40.FIN2	52	0.972	0.81	0.03	0.0969	0.0028	0.4159	599	17	596	16	575	79	596	16	0.500834725
13_V15_1_27.FIN2	134.7	0.663	0.834	0.031	0.0975	0.0033	0.57031	613	17	599	19	665	71	599	19	2.283849918
13_V15_1_3.FIN2	150	1.35	0.837	0.014	0.0993	0.0013	0.23329	617.7	7.9	610.4	7.6	631	42	610.4	7.6	1.181803464
13_V15_1_73.FIN2	297	0.831	0.852	0.02	0.0996	0.0026	0.65267	624	11	612	15	666	44	612	15	1.923076923
13_V15_1_100.FIN2	74.9	0.962	0.828	0.026	0.1	0.0031	0.60126	610	14	614	18	596	62	614	18	0.655737705
13_V15_1_119.FIN2	126.3	0.48	0.924	0.018	0.1069	0.0014	0.28174	663.3	9.7	654.6	8.1	699	43	654.6	8.1	1.3116237
13_V15_1_83.FIN2	187.2	0.765	0.939	0.021	0.1077	0.002	0.43728	671	11	659	12	723	43	659	12	1.788375559
13_V15_1_75.FIN2	304	18.5	0.941	0.016	0.1097	0.0019	0.52983	672	8.4	671	11	683	34	671	11	0.148809524
13_V15_1_98.FIN2	393	4.03	1.011	0.02	0.1118	0.002	0.69737	708	10	683	12	797	27	683	12	3.531073446
13_V15_1_41.FIN2	257	4.1	1.054	0.035	0.1192	0.0041	0.61638	728	18	724	24	737	61	724	24	0.549450549
13_V15_1_108.FIN2	149.6	0.901	1.047	0.022	0.119	0.0024	0.45142	726	11	724	14	739	49	724	14	0.275482094
13_V15_1_12.FIN2	176.5	0.993	1.157	0.03	0.1276	0.0042	0.51008	778	14	772	24	813	56	772	24	0.771208226
13_V15_1_43.FIN2	168	7.7	1.71	0.14	0.15	0.011	0.85963	957	60	889	63	1189	96	889	63	7.10553814
13_V15_1_66.FIN2	39.6	0.764	1.596	0.072	0.1525	0.0051	0.41625	966	29	914	28	1045	92	914	28	5.383022774
13_V15_1_69.FIN2	178	0.531	1.677	0.038	0.1666	0.0032	0.64002	997	14	993	18	1008	34	993	18	0.401203611
13_V15_1_44.FIN2	125.4	0.898	1.807	0.031	0.1772	0.0028	0.53153	1048	12	1051	15	1037	33	1037	33	1.350048216

13_V15_1_13.FIN2	172	3.42	1.902	0.059	0.1767	0.0063	0.5975	1075	22	1046	34	1151	56	1151	56	9.122502172	
13_V15_1_10.FIN2	126.5	1.009	2.047	0.044	0.1863	0.0035	0.61752	1131	14	1101	19	1181	36	1181	36	6.773920406	
13_V15_1_7.FIN2	35.3	1.091	2.899	0.085	0.2291	0.0064	0.52821	1377	22	1328	34	1438	50	1438	50	7.649513213	
13_V15_1_81.FIN2	138.9	1.1	3.133	0.042	0.2498	0.0032	0.52534	1439	10	1437	17	1447	24	1447	24	0.691085003	
13_V15_1_59.FIN2	127.6	1.422	3.318	0.065	0.2592	0.004	0.80376	1484	15	1485	21	1479	22	1479	22	0.405679513	
13_V15_1_28.FIN2	317	2.52	3.382	0.067	0.2626	0.0064	0.69348	1500	16	1501	32	1510	31	1510	31	0.59602649	
13_V15_1_114.FIN2	86.3	0.8961	3.244	0.051	0.2487	0.0034	0.46556	1468	13	1431	17	1518	28	1518	28	5.731225296	
13_V15_1_45.FIN2	57.7	0.3244	3.443	0.049	0.2593	0.0027	0.36114	1515	12	1486	14	1547	25	1547	25	3.943115708	
13_V15_1_109.FIN2	45.9	0.751	3.91	0.084	0.2808	0.0053	0.52135	1611	17	1594	27	1632	35	1632	35	2.328431373	
13_V15_1_60.FIN2	57.83	0.3439	4.056	0.068	0.2885	0.0035	0.31591	1643	14	1633	18	1654	33	1654	33	1.269649335	
13_V15_1_24.FIN2	153.1	2.6	4.115	0.066	0.2918	0.0044	0.69436	1656	14	1652	21	1655	22	1655	22	0.181268882	
13_V15_1_82.FIN2	289	4.27	4.181	0.088	0.295	0.0061	0.59944	1666	17	1669	31	1659	36	1659	36	0.602772755	
13_V15_1_19.FIN2	45.4	0.657	4.146	0.073	0.2906	0.0046	0.51585	1662	15	1647	23	1674	33	1674	33	1.612903226	
13_V15_1_74.FIN2	134.8	0.5603	4.237	0.049	0.2962	0.0038	0.58017	1679.5	9.6	1671	19	1690	20	1690	20	1.124260355	
13_V15_1_23.FIN2	224.1	1.632	4.719	0.069	0.3258	0.0054	0.43437	1770	13	1820	25	1707	30	1707	30	6.61980082	
13_V15_1_4.FIN2	367	2.47	4.791	0.063	0.3146	0.0048	0.54834	1783	11	1763	23	1780	23	1780	23	0.95505618	
13_V15_1_113.FIN2	12.91	0.591	4.82	0.13	0.3037	0.006	0.26782	1783	22	1708	29	1873	52	1873	52	8.80939669	
13_V15_1_49.FIN2	175.3	0.853	6.019	0.08	0.3642	0.0054	0.58568	1979	12	2001	25	1954	23	1954	23	2.405322416	
13_V15_1_29.FIN2	44.9	0.5325	6.479	0.082	0.3828	0.005	0.50521	2041	11	2088	23	1989	23	1989	23	4.977375566	
13_V15_1_57.FIN2	57.8	0.753	5.88	0.11	0.343	0.0066	0.52147	1957	16	1900	32	2014	30	2014	30	5.660377358	
13_V15_1_77.FIN2	146.6	1.846	7.564	0.088	0.4014	0.0054	0.65856	2179	10	2174	25	2182	17	2182	17	0.366636114	
13_V15_1_88.FIN2	313	0.91	7.9	0.16	0.4046	0.0087	0.64259	2217	18	2188	40	2256	26	2256	26	3.014184397	
13_V15_1_97.FIN2	370	11.6	11.22	0.17	0.5092	0.0092	0.83636	2538	14	2653	38	2454	15	2454	15	8.109209454	
sample 15AP39	coordinates	81°00' 52.7"															
		065°21' 24.2"															
								207/235		206/238		207/206		Best age			
Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	Age Ma	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	(Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*	
15ap39_102.FIN2	187	2.61	0.2323	0.007	0.03329	0.00046	0.40664	211.7	5.8	211.1	2.9	214	57	211.1	2.9	0.283419934	
15ap39_81.FIN2	153	0.4187	0.2686	0.0081	0.03596	0.00065	0.087195	242.3	6.8	227.7	4.1	360	76	227.7	4.1	6.025588114	
15ap39_101.FIN2	361	0.921	0.2631	0.0089	0.03722	0.00058	0.047414	236.9	7.1	235.6	3.6	245	81	235.6	3.6	0.548754749	
15ap39_106.FIN2	213	0.488	0.2654	0.0094	0.03733	0.00094	0.53411	238.6	7.5	236.2	5.9	252	67	236.2	5.9	1.005867561	
15ap39_7.FIN2	235	1.06	0.285	0.016	0.03805	0.00081	0.065549	248.5	6.5	240.6	5.1	294	64	240.6	5.1	3.179074447	
15ap39_38.FIN2	105	0.985	0.298	0.013	0.03893	0.00093	0.38277	263	11	246.1	5.8	383	91	246.1	5.8	6.425855513	
15ap39_113.FIN2	413	0.813	0.2853	0.0078	0.03894	0.00077	0.27317	254.7	6.2	246.2	4.8	338	65	246.2	4.8	3.337259521	
15ap39_107.FIN2	278.7	1.108	0.3093	0.0085	0.04263	0.00083	0.51475	273.4	6.6	269.1	5.1	312	54	269.1	5.1	1.572787125	
15ap39_37.FIN2	235	0.93	0.3358	0.009	0.04444	0.00082	0.27627	293.4	6.9	280.2	5.1	389	61	280.2	5.1	4.498977505	
15ap39_12.FIN2	154.5	0.486	0.344	0.012	0.0463	0.0013	0.17455	301.2	8.8	291.9	7.8	344	90	291.9	7.8	3.087649402	
15ap39_70.FIN2	298	0.799	0.355	0.014	0.0467	0.0017	0.22961	308	10	294	11	426	76	294	11	4.545454545	
15ap39_13.FIN2	80.2	0.652	0.352	0.012	0.0471	0.0011	0.20302	305.8	8.7	296.7	6.5	360	78	296.7	6.5	2.975801177	
15ap39_65.FIN2	96.1	0.648	0.352	0.011	0.04762	0.00094	0.27694	305.2	8.6	300.7	6	333	71	300.7	6	1.474442988	
15ap39_128.FIN2	227	0.775	0.398	0.011	0.0501	0.0013	0.53468	339	7.7	314.8	7.8	496	55	314.8	7.8	7.138643068	
15ap39_130.FIN2	187.5	1.077	0.382	0.011	0.0501	0.0013	0.13846	327.3	8.1	314.8	7.9	416	55	314.8	7.9	3.819126184	
15ap39_97.FIN2	98.6	0.809	0.399	0.014	0.05054	0.00079	0.15187	340	9.9	317.8	4.8	470	77	317.8	4.8	6.529411765	
15ap39_23.FIN2	153	1.604	0.399	0.016	0.0512	0.0015	0.42887	339	11	321.7	9	419	79	321.7	9	5.103244838	
15ap39_27.FIN2	257	1.448	0.398	0.011	0.052	0.0017	0.33671	339.4	8	326	11	418	77	326	11	3.948143783	

15ap39_129.FIN2	133	1.126	0.407	0.014	0.0519	0.0011	0.67837	344.8	9.7	326.2	6.7	451	64	326.2	6.7	5.394431555
15ap39_62.FIN2	131.4	1.649	0.4301	0.0094	0.0523	0.0006	0.38083	362.6	6.7	328.6	3.7	584	46	328.6	3.7	9.376723662
15ap39_91.FIN2	146.2	0.699	0.416	0.013	0.05242	0.00098	0.24387	352.3	9.2	329.3	6	485	66	329.3	6	6.528526824
15ap39_4.FIN2	67.2	0.746	0.408	0.014	0.05269	0.00082	0.032882	346	10	331	5	423	80	331	5	4.335260116
15ap39_93.FIN2	262.7	0.672	0.421	0.011	0.0535	0.001	0.28412	356.4	7.5	336.8	6	488	49	336.8	6	5.499438833
15ap39_104.FIN2	169.9	1.577	0.4097	0.0097	0.05431	0.0008	0.31463	348.1	7	340.9	4.9	391	52	340.9	4.9	2.068371158
15ap39_126.FIN2	92.1	0.852	0.407	0.014	0.0552	0.0012	0.21843	345	10	346.1	7.5	353	81	346.1	7.5	-0.31884058
15ap39_73.FIN2	114	1.367	0.418	0.012	0.05566	0.00083	0.22194	353.2	8.4	349.1	5.1	368	62	349.1	5.1	1.160815402
15ap39_22.FIN2	64.3	0.915	0.452	0.015	0.0572	0.001	0.06774	378	11	358.7	6.4	484	83	358.7	6.4	5.105820106
15ap39_115.FIN2	113.1	0.704	0.432	0.012	0.05736	0.00082	0.28815	364.1	8.6	359.5	5	408	64	359.5	5	1.263389179
15ap39_5.FIN2	352	0.683	0.4491	0.0073	0.0577	0.00091	0.45912	376.4	5.1	361.6	5.5	459	37	361.6	5.5	3.931987248
15ap39_41.FIN2	93.7	1.119	0.474	0.016	0.0596	0.0015	0.16916	393	11	373.1	9.2	512	84	373.1	9.2	5.063613232
15ap39_75.FIN2	43.09	1.364	0.507	0.015	0.0605	0.0011	0.15617	415	10	378.5	6.8	590	72	378.5	6.8	8.795180723
15ap39_44.FIN2	505	2.47	0.507	0.014	0.063	0.0016	0.67787	416	9.6	396	11	538	51	396	11	4.807692308
15ap39_17.FIN2	496	3.85	0.4923	0.0092	0.0635	0.0012	0.4463	406	6.2	396.7	7	453	41	396.7	7	2.290640394
15ap39_88.FIN2	632	0.927	0.485	0.011	0.0633	0.0014	0.64154	400.7	7.3	397	8.8	417	42	397	8.8	0.923384078
15ap39_39.FIN2	207	2.43	0.514	0.015	0.0643	0.0012	0.3033	420.4	9.7	401.9	7	502	63	401.9	7	4.400570885
15ap39_114.FIN2	407	1.444	0.506	0.011	0.0651	0.0012	0.48851	415.3	7.6	406.4	7.3	468	47	406.4	7.3	2.143029136
15ap39_84.FIN2	140.3	0.771	0.545	0.017	0.067	0.0013	0.30849	440	11	417.7	7.6	533	66	417.7	7.6	5.068181818
15ap39_61.FIN2	84.4	0.805	0.564	0.017	0.068	0.0015	0.19637	454	11	424	8.8	607	75	424	8.8	6.607929515
15ap39_80.FIN2	348	3.366	0.5277	0.0089	0.0681	0.001	0.39564	429.8	5.9	424.5	6.2	441	41	424.5	6.2	1.233131689
15ap39_77.FIN2	49.9	1.184	0.549	0.018	0.0681	0.0013	0.35453	445	13	424.8	7.9	529	70	424.8	7.9	4.539325843
15ap39_57.FIN2	125	1.39	0.575	0.016	0.0688	0.0011	0.34248	460	10	428.9	6.9	609	59	428.9	6.9	6.760869565
15ap39_90.FIN2	83.2	1.093	0.578	0.016	0.0696	0.0011	0.5175	461	10	434.4	7	604	59	434.4	7	5.770065076
15ap39_52.FIN2	242	1.109	0.543	0.011	0.0698	0.0015	0.38953	439.2	7.5	434.6	9.2	459	54	434.6	9.2	1.047358834
15ap39_53.FIN2	411	17.1	0.585	0.014	0.0709	0.0012	0.47028	466.9	8.6	441.4	7.5	587	44	441.4	7.5	5.461554937
15ap39_99.FIN2	980	102.6	0.5535	0.0097	0.0711	0.0013	0.58274	446.8	6.4	442.9	7.9	466	37	442.9	7.9	0.872873769
15ap39_112.FIN2	124	1.249	0.586	0.017	0.0713	0.0011	0.19538	467	11	443.9	6.4	574	63	443.9	6.4	4.946466809
15ap39_69.FIN2	235	2.618	0.585	0.012	0.0719	0.0013	0.50588	467.1	7.9	447.4	7.8	562	43	447.4	7.8	4.21751231
15ap39_87.FIN2	199.8	0.3917	0.574	0.012	0.072	0.0011	0.18062	460.2	7.9	447.8	6.4	513	49	447.8	6.4	2.694480661
15ap39_82.FIN2	119.4	0.637	0.619	0.017	0.0721	0.0012	0.46732	488	10	448.5	7.1	662	52	448.5	7.1	8.094262295
15ap39_67.FIN2	75	1.055	0.585	0.02	0.0724	0.0016	0.36465	466	12	450.5	9.5	535	69	450.5	9.5	3.326180258
15ap39_26.FIN2	439	2.88	0.577	0.011	0.0729	0.0011	0.59603	462	6.8	453.3	6.7	492	35	453.3	6.7	1.883116883
15ap39_109.FIN2	285	1.015	0.574	0.01	0.0734	0.0012	0.35187	461.2	6.8	456.6	7.2	489	42	456.6	7.2	0.997398092
15ap39_51.FIN2	151.7	0.68	0.595	0.014	0.0746	0.0015	0.39333	473.5	8.7	463.9	9.2	520	54	463.9	9.2	2.027455121
15ap39_8.FIN2	294	0.681	0.591	0.011	0.0749	0.001	0.025327	470.6	7.2	465.4	6.1	486	38	465.4	6.1	1.104972376
15ap39_19.FIN2	209.9	0.46	0.596	0.02	0.0771	0.0027	0.50142	473	13	478	16	430	74	478	16	-1.057082452
15ap39_31.FIN2	109.6	0.903	0.614	0.017	0.0776	0.0018	0.39144	484	10	482	11	481	55	482	11	0.41322314
15ap39_76.FIN2	162.5	1.502	0.668	0.012	0.078	0.0012	0.26638	518.8	7.6	484.4	7.3	670	45	484.4	7.3	6.630686199
15ap39_33.FIN2	48.4	2.19	0.701	0.023	0.0823	0.0015	0.12603	539	13	509.9	8.9	643	74	509.9	8.9	5.398886827
15ap39_103.FIN2	162.4	0.754	0.732	0.019	0.0892	0.0021	0.41809	557	11	551	13	584	58	551	13	1.077199282
15ap39_95.FIN2	286.7	30.25	0.804	0.012	0.0972	0.0013	0.43854	599.3	6.5	597.5	7.9	589	32	597.5	7.9	0.300350409
15ap39_100.FIN2	283.1	29.83	0.815	0.012	0.0977	0.0012	0.34794	604.5	6.7	600.6	7.3	613	34	600.6	7.3	0.64516129
15ap39_55.FIN2	72.8	0.5262	0.957	0.022	0.1039	0.0016	0.26343	680	11	637	9.1	831	48	637	9.1	6.323529412
15ap39_105.FIN2	94.9	0.797	0.976	0.021	0.1049	0.0015	0.1366	690	11	643.1	8.7	851	52	643.1	8.7	6.797101449

15ap39_45.FIN2	263	1.447	0.906	0.016	0.1068	0.002	0.57656	654.7	8.6	654	12	672	36	654	12	0.1069192	
15ap39_66.FIN2	118	0.807	1.063	0.026	0.1165	0.0017	0.32353	734	12	710	9.7	807	47	710	9.7	3.269754768	
15ap39_92.FIN2	137.1	0.943	1.221	0.023	0.1323	0.0022	0.38586	809	11	801	13	831	41	801	13	0.988875155	
15ap39_118.FIN2	591	4.03	1.501	0.075	0.145	0.0063	0.87327	915	31	869	36	1032	42	869	36	5.027322404	
15ap39_121.FIN2	223.7	2.34	1.712	0.029	0.1619	0.0028	0.39028	1012	11	967	15	1116	38	967	15	4.446640316	
15ap39_110.FIN2	164.3	1.771	1.715	0.029	0.1694	0.0024	0.41937	1013	11	1009	13	1020	34	1020	34	1.078431373	
15ap39_28.FIN2	71	1.361	1.855	0.058	0.1756	0.0048	0.099172	1058	20	1041	26	1085	59	1085	59	4.055299539	
15ap39_68.FIN2	545	3.14	1.797	0.028	0.1716	0.0025	0.41866	1044.9	9.9	1020	14	1113	27	1113	27	8.355795148	
15ap39_78.FIN2	307	1.421	2.097	0.034	0.1977	0.0036	0.55694	1147	11	1162	19	1118	32	1118	32	-3.935599284	
15ap39_96.FIN2	146	2.026	2.137	0.039	0.1967	0.0034	0.43111	1158	12	1157	18	1168	34	1168	34	0.941780822	
15ap39_94.FIN2	71.3	1.842	2.124	0.04	0.1938	0.0027	0.53157	1154	13	1142	15	1173	33	1173	33	2.642796249	
15ap39_30.FIN2	71.1	1.613	2.441	0.057	0.2049	0.004	0.60322	1252	17	1201	22	1333	37	1333	37	9.902475619	
15ap39_32.FIN2	166.2	1.15	3.099	0.058	0.2442	0.0042	0.24403	1430	14	1408	22	1458	33	1458	33	3.429355281	
15ap39_3.FIN2	167.2	2.03	3.687	0.065	0.2798	0.0058	0.65994	1566	14	1589	29	1537	33	1537	33	-3.383214053	
15ap39_18.FIN2	211.4	3.1	3.59	0.11	0.2698	0.0085	0.62066	1544	24	1548	40	1545	50	1545	50	-0.194174757	
15ap39_99.FIN2	75.3	2.261	3.67	0.15	0.2684	0.0087	0.77378	1560	32	1532	44	1602	52	1602	52	4.369538077	
15ap39_108.FIN2	119.9	0.782	4.209	0.059	0.2981	0.0038	0.63354	1675	12	1681	19	1669	23	1669	23	-0.718993409	
15ap39_83.FIN2	69.8	1.486	4.105	0.055	0.2881	0.004	0.17813	1654	11	1631	20	1681	31	1681	31	2.974419988	
15ap39_40.FIN2	56.1	0.57	3.87	0.13	0.2652	0.0075	0.18004	1593	22	1520	40	1688	49	1688	49	9.952606635	
15ap39_79.FIN2	144	3.17	4.105	0.08	0.2861	0.0043	0.61337	1652	16	1621	21	1691	29	1691	29	4.139562389	
15ap39_117.FIN2	108	0.713	4.548	0.086	0.3098	0.0062	0.57153	1739	15	1737	30	1751	32	1751	32	0.799543118	
15ap39_85.FIN2	162.4	1.92	4.28	0.057	0.286	0.0043	0.53245	1688	11	1621	22	1771	25	1771	25	8.469791078	
15ap39_9.FIN2	75.9	1.491	4.9	0.19	0.3172	0.0086	0.27011	1782	27	1777	41	1781	57	1781	57	0.224592925	
15ap39_25.FIN2	47.6	0.515	4.714	0.077	0.3067	0.0046	0.52671	1767	14	1723	23	1807	29	1807	29	4.648588821	
15ap39_24.FIN2	165	0.562	5.314	0.088	0.3388	0.0045	0.44213	1870	14	1879	22	1859	22	1859	22	-1.07584723	
15ap39_20.FIN2	45.5	1.289	5.404	0.083	0.3401	0.0042	0.31601	1883	13	1889	21	1871	29	1871	29	-0.962052378	
15ap39_64.FIN2	37.5	2.502	5.8	0.12	0.3494	0.0068	0.55702	1945	18	1930	32	1955	34	1955	34	1.278772379	
15ap39_98.FIN2	90.6	0.83	5.35	0.11	0.3189	0.0039	0.53202	1873	17	1784	19	1971	30	1971	30	9.487569762	
15ap39_111.FIN2	83.5	0.508	6.42	0.19	0.3504	0.0092	0.30763	2025	25	1932	44	2128	50	2128	50	9.210526316	
15ap39_116.FIN2	206.5	0.975	8.6	0.13	0.4281	0.006	0.67577	2297	13	2299	26	2297	20	2297	20	-0.087070091	
15ap39_47.FIN2	58.7	6.31	12.24	0.33	0.481	0.011	0.61084	2617	26	2529	46	2690	37	2690	37	5.985130112	
15ap39_120.FIN2	120	2.15	13.55	0.18	0.5173	0.0072	0.62321	2717	13	2686	30	2749	18	2749	18	2.291742452	
15ap39_125.FIN2	60.6	0.814	12.8	0.3	0.4806	0.0095	0.68507	2659	21	2526	41	2773	30	2773	30	8.907320591	
sample 18-v15-1	coordinates	81°00.883'															
		065°21.395'															
								207/235		206/238		207/206		Best age			
Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	Age Ma	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	(Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*	
18_V15_1_1.FIN2	271.8	45.6	0.3977	0.0071	0.05375	0.00059	0.39892	339.6	5.1	337.5	3.6	345	38	337.5	3.6	0.618374558	
18_V15_1_10.FIN2	643	1.529	4.856	0.05	0.3155	0.0048	0.29509	1793.8	8.7	1771	23	1820	24	1820	24	2.692307692	
18_V15_1_100.FIN2	42.7	0.943	3.796	0.063	0.2786	0.0032	0.31384	1590	13	1584	16	1601	32	1601	32	1.061836352	
18_V15_1_101.FIN2	116.4	0.606	9.93	0.15	0.4566	0.0069	0.74962	2426	13	2423	31	2435	18	2435	18	0.492813142	
18_V15_1_102.FIN2	327.7	3.61	5.375	0.077	0.3433	0.0045	0.57902	1879	12	1901	21	1859	23	1859	23	-2.259279182	
18_V15_1_103.FIN2	75.1	1.55	0.471	0.012	0.0627	0.00084	0.24692	390.6	8.3	391.9	5.1	378	55	391.9	5.1	-0.332821301	
18_V15_1_104.FIN2	73.4	0.657	0.367	0.011	0.04544	0.00093	0.3448	316.7	8.5	286.4	5.8	539	69	286.4	5.8	9.567413956	
18_V15_1_105.FIN2	306.3	0.819	0.4452	0.0074	0.05837	0.0007	0.54736	373.4	5.2	365.7	4.2	417	32	365.7	4.2	2.062131762	

18_V15_1_106.FIN2	31.8	0.593	5.21	0.12	0.3275	0.0047	0.41554	1850	20	1825	23	1884	37	1884	37	3.13163482
18_V15_1_107.FIN2	182	2.99	0.62	0.021	0.0744	0.0014	0.31384	488	13	462.2	8.4	595	68	462.2	8.4	5.286885246
18_V15_1_108.FIN2	156	0.523	0.3647	0.0093	0.0482	0.0006	0.24139	315	6.8	303.4	3.7	390	54	303.4	3.7	3.682539683
18_V15_1_109.FIN2	471	1.181	0.5459	0.0063	0.07024	0.00076	0.35233	442	4.1	437.6	4.6	468	27	437.6	4.6	0.995475113
18_V15_1_11.FIN2	113.5	0.919	0.425	0.012	0.05576	0.00088	0.44681	358.2	8.6	349.7	5.4	404	56	349.7	5.4	2.372975991
18_V15_1_110.FIN2	266	2.065	0.4267	0.0086	0.0535	0.0011	0.40637	360.5	6.1	336	7	521	51	336	7	6.796116505
18_V15_1_111.FIN2	278.5	1.326	0.2174	0.006	0.03061	0.0007	0.32293	199.4	5.1	194.4	4.4	263	65	194.4	4.4	2.507522568
18_V15_1_112.FIN2	100.2	0.4126	0.544	0.012	0.06871	0.00091	0.26806	440.2	8.1	428.3	5.5	495	53	428.3	5.5	2.703316674
18_V15_1_113.FIN2	181	0.937	0.824	0.014	0.098	0.0013	0.47724	609.1	7.8	602.6	7.6	628	34	602.6	7.6	1.067148252
18_V15_1_114.FIN2	52.8	1.034	4.015	0.065	0.2926	0.0039	0.47881	1635	13	1654	20	1604	30	1604	30	-3.117206983
18_V15_1_115.FIN2	346	0.905	0.607	0.011	0.0766	0.0012	0.4652	480.9	6.8	475.7	7.1	505	36	475.7	7.1	1.081305885
18_V15_1_116.FIN2	138.4	1.959	1.662	0.028	0.1654	0.002	0.473	992	11	986	11	1002	31	986	11	0.60483871
18_V15_1_117.FIN2	85	0.67	0.496	0.013	0.06488	0.00089	0.40857	407.7	8.6	405.1	5.4	398	55	405.1	5.4	0.637723817
18_V15_1_118.FIN2	133.9	0.4717	0.3177	0.0072	0.04442	0.00056	0.38097	279.6	5.5	280.2	3.4	254	44	280.2	3.4	-0.214592275
18_V15_1_119.FIN2	127.1	3.44	5.159	0.074	0.3397	0.0051	0.66673	1844	12	1884	24	1799	23	1799	23	-4.724847137
18_V15_1_12.FIN2	116	1.035	0.388	0.012	0.04992	0.00085	0.20602	333.2	9.3	314	5.2	443	72	314	5.2	5.762304922
18_V15_1_120.FIN2	102.8	1.301	0.613	0.014	0.0769	0.0011	0.33292	485.5	8.6	477.6	6.7	502	50	477.6	6.7	1.627188465
18_V15_1_121.FIN2	287	2.58	1.56	0.02	0.1595	0.0022	0.49294	953.6	7.9	954	12	938	28	954	12	-0.041946309
18_V15_1_122.FIN2	84.1	1.157	1.671	0.027	0.1683	0.0024	0.45747	997.9	9.9	1002	13	971	33	971	13	-0.410862812
18_V15_1_123.FIN2	124.4	0.893	0.414	0.013	0.0549	0.0013	0.50733	350.3	9.2	344.7	8	358	61	344.7	8	1.598629746
18_V15_1_124.FIN2	97.5	0.793	5.227	0.096	0.3457	0.0061	0.58922	1857	15	1912	29	1779	30	1779	30	-7.476110174
18_V15_1_125.FIN2	114.6	0.57	0.3589	0.0093	0.04908	0.00066	0.21963	310.7	6.9	308.8	4	297	58	308.8	4	0.611522369
18_V15_1_126.FIN2	96.1	0.386	6.148	0.087	0.3638	0.0044	0.4016	1996	13	1999	21	1974	26	1974	26	-1.266464032
18_V15_1_128.FIN2	94.5	0.716	0.455	0.012	0.05948	0.00076	0.25355	380	8.5	372.4	4.6	393	58	372.4	4.6	2
18_V15_1_13.FIN2	22.68	0.1027	4.7	0.097	0.3062	0.0063	0.65522	1766	18	1720	31	1834	39	1834	39	6.215921483
18_V15_1_130.FIN2	71.2	1.579	4.86	0.065	0.3226	0.0036	0.37208	1794	11	1802	18	1766	26	1766	26	-2.038505096
18_V15_1_14.FIN2	16.2	0.607	4.47	0.11	0.2961	0.0056	0.28386	1724	20	1671	28	1788	53	1788	53	6.543624161
18_V15_1_16.FIN2	646	1.031	0.2753	0.0061	0.03646	0.00059	0.38584	246.7	4.8	230.8	3.7	393	49	230.8	3.7	6.44507499
18_V15_1_17.FIN2	297	1.11	2.123	0.044	0.1933	0.0048	0.42643	1154	14	1138	26	1187	47	1187	47	4.128053917
18_V15_1_18.FIN2	163	1.655	0.3313	0.0085	0.04487	0.00065	0.38359	289.8	6.5	282.9	4	323	53	282.9	4	2.380952381
18_V15_1_19.FIN2	486.2	0.438	0.3501	0.0065	0.04748	0.00063	0.48343	304.5	4.9	299	3.9	341	36	299	3.9	1.806239737
18_V15_1_2.FIN2	157.4	1.726	0.3763	0.0078	0.051	0.00055	0.2915	323.8	5.8	320.7	3.4	339	46	320.7	3.4	0.957381099
18_V15_1_20.FIN2	86.2	1.009	0.3659	0.0098	0.04723	0.00063	0.16478	316.8	7.5	297.5	3.8	448	64	297.5	3.8	6.092171717
18_V15_1_21.FIN2	95.2	0.78	0.364	0.011	0.04855	0.00079	0.17495	314.1	8.4	305.5	4.9	354	71	305.5	4.9	2.737981535
18_V15_1_22.FIN2	224	1.763	0.326	0.013	0.0431	0.0017	0.5349	285.3	9.6	272	10	399	78	272	10	4.661759551
18_V15_1_23.FIN2	17.94	2.509	0.458	0.024	0.0562	0.0018	0.31839	381	17	354	11	540	110	354	11	7.086614173
18_V15_1_24.FIN2	77.3	0.3997	4.2	0.076	0.2952	0.0045	0.37319	1672	15	1667	23	1675	35	1675	35	0.47761194
18_V15_1_25.FIN2	318.5	1.5	0.3339	0.0057	0.04599	0.00062	0.3555	292.3	4.4	289.8	3.8	302	39	289.8	3.8	0.855285665
18_V15_1_26.FIN2	197.7	1.57	6.89	0.34	0.367	0.018	0.76437	2078	46	2021	91	2153	68	2153	68	6.130980028
18_V15_1_27.FIN2	56.5	0.712	0.434	0.014	0.05765	0.0009	0.14315	364.6	9.6	361.2	5.5	368	69	361.2	5.5	0.932528799
18_V15_1_28.FIN2	113.7	1.13	0.264	0.011	0.0346	0.0011	0.33192	237	8.4	219.3	6.8	401	86	219.3	6.8	7.46835443
18_V15_1_3.FIN2	26.7	0.629	0.41	0.021	0.0522	0.0013	0.20352	346	15	327.9	7.8	450	120	327.9	7.8	5.231213873
18_V15_1_30.FIN2	71.2	0.926	0.416	0.013	0.05559	0.00083	0.3251	351.3	9.7	348.7	5	341	66	348.7	5	0.74010817
18_V15_1_32.FIN2	189	0.743	0.3585	0.0075	0.04877	0.0007	0.19649	310.6	5.6	306.9	4.3	319	50	306.9	4.3	1.191242756
18_V15_1_33.FIN2	179.8	0.92	5.46	0.065	0.3403	0.0043	0.48613	1893	10	1887	21	1891	23	1891	23	0.211528292

18_V15_1_35.FIN2	46.5	0.452	6.62	0.15	0.3705	0.0095	0.66112	2057	21	2027	45	2072	37	2072	37	2.171814672
18_V15_1_36.FIN2	40.8	0.984	0.771	0.026	0.0907	0.0018	0.27917	580	14	560	11	623	70	560	11	3.448275862
18_V15_1_38.FIN2	395	4.24	0.752	0.021	0.0904	0.0019	0.72198	568	12	558	11	609	51	558	11	1.76056338
18_V15_1_39.FIN2	381	1.61	0.3807	0.0062	0.05083	0.00075	0.13082	327.3	4.5	319.6	4.6	366	37	319.6	4.6	2.352581729
18_V15_1_4.FIN2	49.7	1.142	0.417	0.014	0.0557	0.001	0.11686	352.4	9.9	349.2	6.1	370	73	349.2	6.1	0.908059024
18_V15_1_40.FIN2	392	1.362	6.172	0.096	0.3655	0.0056	0.58999	2003	13	2006	27	1984	24	1984	24	-1.108870968
18_V15_1_41.FIN2	245	1.85	0.3216	0.009	0.0446	0.00088	0.33731	283.1	7	281.2	5.4	272	60	281.2	5.4	0.67114094
18_V15_1_42.FIN2	98.5	0.773	0.639	0.017	0.0778	0.0015	0.37857	501	11	482.8	9	555	57	482.8	9	3.632734531
18_V15_1_43.FIN2	178	0.5691	0.701	0.012	0.084	0.0011	0.33977	539.1	7.4	519.7	6.7	607	41	519.7	6.7	3.598590243
18_V15_1_44.FIN2	540	1.006	0.617	0.016	0.0782	0.0018	0.5129	488	9.5	485	11	461	50	485	11	0.614754098
18_V15_1_45.FIN2	687	19.9	0.594	0.01	0.0744	0.001	0.53372	472.5	6.4	462.6	6.1	496	33	462.6	6.1	2.095238095
18_V15_1_47.FIN2	121.1	0.247	0.3374	0.0094	0.04618	0.00064	0.30958	294.3	7	291	4	306	59	291	4	1.121304791
18_V15_1_48.FIN2	43.1	3.39	0.412	0.015	0.0553	0.0012	0.20086	350	11	347	7.1	359	84	347	7.1	0.857142857
18_V15_1_49.FIN2	268	0.735	0.495	0.013	0.0595	0.0013	0.39687	407.3	8.9	372.5	7.7	576	58	372.5	7.7	8.54407071
18_V15_1_5.FIN2	66.7	1.203	4.45	0.12	0.2898	0.0055	0.51695	1715	22	1639	27	1803	42	1803	42	9.095951192
18_V15_1_50.FIN2	258	1.511	0.3769	0.0082	0.0512	0.001	0.42833	324.1	6	321.5	6.3	336	50	321.5	6.3	0.802221537
18_V15_1_52.FIN2	450	3.067	0.2671	0.0067	0.03535	0.00077	0.39747	240.1	5.4	223.9	4.8	385	57	223.9	4.8	6.747188671
18_V15_1_53.FIN2	90.1	1.439	0.394	0.013	0.0509	0.0014	0.42823	336.1	9.8	320.1	8.3	424	74	320.1	8.3	4.76048795
18_V15_1_54.FIN2	158	1.203	0.33	0.019	0.0444	0.0011	0.36197	288	14	280	7	320	110	280	7	2.777777778
18_V15_1_55.FIN2	74.2	0.698	0.415	0.018	0.054	0.0011	0.10182	351	13	339	6.5	399	98	339	6.5	3.418803419
18_V15_1_56.FIN2	31.7	1.994	0.451	0.03	0.0564	0.0023	0.26637	373	20	353	14	430	130	353	14	5.361930295
18_V15_1_57.FIN2	193	2.5	0.399	0.01	0.05014	0.00094	0.14744	340.2	7.2	315.3	5.7	479	62	315.3	5.7	7.319223986
18_V15_1_58.FIN2	107.6	2.711	13.19	0.37	0.51	0.016	0.69025	2683	27	2645	68	2715	38	2715	38	2.578268877
18_V15_1_6.FIN2	156	0.848	0.362	0.013	0.04883	0.00099	0.19345	312	10	307.2	6.1	337	79	307.2	6.1	1.538461538
18_V15_1_60.FIN2	946	22.5	0.7288	0.0087	0.0861	0.0011	0.57242	555.5	5.1	532.6	6.2	647	24	532.6	6.2	4.122412241
18_V15_1_61.FIN2	220	0.538	0.733	0.012	0.08926	0.00099	0.42606	557.7	6.9	551.1	5.8	573	32	551.1	5.8	1.183431953
18_V15_1_62.FIN2	175	1.029	0.716	0.016	0.0808	0.0013	0.4247	547.4	9.3	501.1	7.7	729	46	501.1	7.7	8.458165875
18_V15_1_63.FIN2	75.5	1.222	1.767	0.031	0.1722	0.0023	0.37825	1031	11	1024	13	1027	35	1027	35	0.29211295
18_V15_1_65.FIN2	75.1	0.591	0.563	0.016	0.07	0.0011	0.12977	452	11	436	6.3	497	68	436	6.3	3.539823009
18_V15_1_66.FIN2	229.9	0.673	0.3335	0.0088	0.04412	0.00089	0.35513	291.6	6.7	278.2	5.5	382	59	278.2	5.5	4.595336077
18_V15_1_68.FIN2	409	0.636	0.532	0.011	0.0657	0.0012	0.64424	431.9	7.5	409.9	7.4	538	38	409.9	7.4	5.093771706
18_V15_1_69.FIN2	166	1.57	0.548	0.021	0.0692	0.0021	0.52022	440	14	431	13	469	72	431	13	2.045454545
18_V15_1_7.FIN2	352	1.65	1.381	0.019	0.1445	0.0019	0.51998	880	8.3	870	11	907	27	870	11	1.136363636
18_V15_1_70.FIN2	162.7	3.19	6.274	0.075	0.3652	0.005	0.60368	2013	11	2005	24	2020	21	2020	21	0.742574257
18_V15_1_71.FIN2	325	0.702	0.3097	0.0067	0.04312	0.00075	0.44784	273.5	5.2	272.1	4.6	279	46	272.1	4.6	0.511882998
18_V15_1_72.FIN2	66.8	0.7416	0.55	0.017	0.07	0.0011	0.14454	444	11	435.9	6.8	460	71	435.9	6.8	1.824324324
18_V15_1_73.FIN2	73.4	1.053	0.338	0.012	0.04614	0.00085	0.17273	294.5	9.1	290.7	5.3	306	77	290.7	5.3	1.290322581
18_V15_1_74.FIN2	137	2.36	0.35	0.012	0.04642	0.00073	0.30134	305.1	9.3	292.4	4.5	390	72	292.4	4.5	4.162569649
18_V15_1_75.FIN2	257	0.714	0.555	0.0088	0.07173	0.00085	0.38308	447.7	5.7	446.5	5.1	451	34	446.5	5.1	0.268036632
18_V15_1_76.FIN2	131.7	1.902	0.567	0.013	0.0674	0.0011	0.32824	455	8.2	420.5	6.6	623	50	420.5	6.6	7.582417582
18_V15_1_77.FIN2	147	1.023	0.39	0.011	0.0516	0.0008	0.30371	333.2	8	324.3	4.9	384	60	324.3	4.9	2.671068427
18_V15_1_78.FIN2	120.2	0.826	0.354	0.012	0.0486	0.0015	0.42834	306.2	9.2	305.6	9.3	304	73	305.6	9.3	0.195950359
18_V15_1_79.FIN2	311	5.86	0.426	0.029	0.0517	0.0033	0.66265	356	20	324	20	540	110	324	20	8.988764045
18_V15_1_8.FIN2	289	0.727	0.2955	0.009	0.042	0.0012	0.3692	262.5	7.1	265.3	7.6	245	71	265.3	7.6	-1.066666667
18_V15_1_80.FIN2	211	1.73	0.4039	0.0086	0.0548	0.00071	0.40073	344.6	6.4	343.9	4.3	338	44	343.9	4.3	0.203134068

18_V15_1_81.FIN2	270.7	0.739	0.807	0.019	0.0984	0.0018	0.73192	601	10	605	11	579	37	605	11	-0.665557404	
18_V15_1_82.FIN2	428	1.159	0.2967	0.0066	0.04123	0.00075	0.50699	264	5.3	260.4	4.7	294	45	260.4	4.7	1.363636364	
18_V15_1_83.FIN2	160	0.668	0.336	0.0083	0.04609	0.00082	0.29403	293.4	6.2	290.4	5	315	55	290.4	5	1.022494888	
18_V15_1_84.FIN2	449	1.723	0.3803	0.0058	0.05069	0.00047	0.29852	327	4.3	318.7	2.9	383	34	318.7	2.9	2.5382263	
18_V15_1_85.FIN2	43.9	0.3921	4.793	0.07	0.3142	0.0036	0.36912	1782	12	1761	18	1817	31	1817	31	3.082003302	
18_V15_1_86.FIN2	225.8	1.489	0.664	0.016	0.082	0.0017	0.54006	515.3	9.6	508	9.9	545	48	508	9.9	1.416650495	
18_V15_1_87.FIN2	343	1.295	0.3452	0.0071	0.0475	0.00068	0.44852	300.6	5.3	299.1	4.2	320	40	299.1	4.2	0.499001996	
18_V15_1_88.FIN2	81.1	1.07	0.436	0.014	0.05715	0.00086	0.001396	366.5	9.8	358.2	5.3	413	73	358.2	5.3	2.264665757	
18_V15_1_89.FIN2	259	0.532	0.5239	0.0088	0.06759	0.0008	0.16773	428.3	6.1	421.6	4.8	467	43	421.6	4.8	1.564324072	
18_V15_1_9.FIN2	316	2.001	0.736	0.014	0.0899	0.0017	0.55203	559.1	8	555	10	579	39	555	10	0.733321409	
18_V15_1_90.FIN2	91.1	1.042	5.264	0.078	0.3267	0.0044	0.6167	1863	12	1821	22	1913	23	1913	23	4.809200209	
18_V15_1_91.FIN2	293	42.4	0.3566	0.0067	0.04884	0.00062	0.39694	309.4	5	307.4	3.8	327	40	307.4	3.8	0.646412411	
18_V15_1_92.FIN2	69.5	0.584	1.73	0.034	0.1638	0.0021	0.38173	1017	13	978	12	1102	36	978	12	3.83480826	
18_V15_1_93.FIN2	204	1.577	0.612	0.037	0.0743	0.0025	0.080664	483	22	462	15	550	120	462	15	4.347826087	
18_V15_1_94.FIN2	290	1.229	0.3669	0.0092	0.049	0.00076	0.37566	316.9	6.9	308.3	4.7	378	53	308.3	4.7	2.713789839	
18_V15_1_95.FIN2	369	13.5	6.17	0.16	0.362	0.01	0.66561	1992	23	1988	49	2006	38	2006	38	0.897308076	
18_V15_1_96.FIN2	79.3	1.708	0.642	0.022	0.0745	0.0017	0.52336	501	14	463	10	663	64	463	10	7.584830339	
18_V15_1_97.FIN2	214	1.18	5.153	0.057	0.3305	0.0039	0.49121	1843.3	9.4	1840	19	1851	20	1851	20	0.594273366	
18_V15_1_98.FIN2	105.6	1.396	0.535	0.011	0.06867	0.0009	0.3737	434.2	7.3	428.1	5.4	469	45	428.1	5.4	1.404882543	
18_V15_1_99.FIN2	93.8	0.552	5.923	0.064	0.3593	0.004	0.47185	1964.7	9.6	1978	19	1957	20	1957	20	-1.073071027	
sample 18-v15-30	coordinates	81°00.883'															
		065°21.395'															
								207/235		206/238		207/206		Best age			
Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	Age Ma	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	(Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*	
18_V15_30_38.FIN2	196.4	1.196	0.2396	0.0074	0.03331	0.00065	0.44466	217.6	6	211.2	4.1	270	61	211.2	4.1	2.941176471	
18_V15_30_82.FIN2	556	1.6	0.2564	0.0055	0.03347	0.00073	0.58341	231.4	4.4	212.2	4.6	428	42	212.2	4.6	8.297320657	
18_V15_30_79.FIN2	343	2.7	0.2458	0.0041	0.03464	0.00043	0.25385	222.9	3.3	219.5	2.7	262	40	219.5	2.7	1.52534769	
18_V15_30_26.FIN2	118.9	1.073	0.2609	0.0071	0.03683	0.00039	0.12381	234.9	5.7	233.1	2.4	240	60	233.1	2.4	0.766283525	
18_V15_30_121.FIN2	167.3	1.988	0.2789	0.0066	0.03956	0.00053	0.093814	249.3	5.2	250.1	3.3	239	52	250.1	3.3	-0.320898516	
18_V15_30_117.FIN2	96.8	0.888	0.2897	0.0074	0.03993	0.00049	0.10693	259.7	6.3	252.4	3	323	61	252.4	3	2.810935695	
18_V15_30_93.FIN2	215.4	0.942	0.3108	0.0094	0.04057	0.00051	0.46784	274.3	7.3	256.3	3.2	414	60	256.3	3.2	6.562158221	
18_V15_30_44.FIN2	219.2	0.5644	0.3105	0.0061	0.04221	0.00041	0.26814	274.8	4.9	266.5	2.6	332	44	266.5	2.6	3.020378457	
18_V15_30_74.FIN2	272	1.97	0.317	0.015	0.0424	0.0024	0.46016	278	11	268	15	410	100	268	15	3.597122302	
18_V15_30_105.FIN2	356	0.746	0.3159	0.0077	0.04258	0.00093	0.50612	279.1	5.7	268.7	5.8	363	52	268.7	5.8	3.726262988	
18_V15_30_59.FIN2	136	1.418	0.3227	0.0098	0.04454	0.00078	0.14753	283	7.6	280.8	4.8	294	70	280.8	4.8	0.777385159	
18_V15_30_65.FIN2	63.6	1.159	0.328	0.014	0.0446	0.001	0.31381	286	11	281.3	6.3	311	87	281.3	6.3	1.643356643	
18_V15_30_39.FIN2	267	1.184	0.3243	0.007	0.04473	0.00079	0.39484	285	5.3	282.1	4.8	300	48	282.1	4.8	1.01754386	
18_V15_30_124.FIN2	310	1.76	0.3485	0.0079	0.04592	0.00076	0.34768	303.2	6	289.4	4.7	414	53	289.4	4.7	4.551451187	
18_V15_30_128.FIN2	11.79	1.137	0.328	0.034	0.046	0.0019	0.41038	283	26	290	11	250	200	290	11	-2.473498233	
18_V15_30_114.FIN2	259.7	2.389	0.3431	0.0057	0.0469	0.0006	0.3987	299.2	4.3	295.4	3.7	322	37	295.4	3.7	1.270053476	
18_V15_30_56.FIN2	170.1	0.659	0.3413	0.0063	0.04729	0.00051	0.34612	297.8	4.8	297.8	3.2	289	40	297.8	3.2	0	
18_V15_30_58.FIN2	157.2	1.433	0.359	0.01	0.04742	0.00086	0.32173	311.7	7.9	298.6	5.3	393	61	298.6	5.3	4.202759063	
18_V15_30_87.FIN2	103.3	2.142	0.347	0.0081	0.0481	0.00064	0.14965	301.8	6	302.8	4	292	50	302.8	4	-0.331345262	
18_V15_30_103.FIN2	490	0.959	0.3645	0.0052	0.04974	0.00056	0.61222	315.3	3.9	312.9	3.5	332	27	312.9	3.5	0.761179829	
18_V15_30_18.FIN2	170	1.08	0.3724	0.0076	0.05036	0.00056	0.36081	320.9	5.6	316.7	3.4	323	43	316.7	3.4	1.308818947	

18_V15_30_83.FIN2	104.1	0.654	0.378	0.011	0.051	0.0011	0.41778	324.7	8.4	320.7	6.7	344	62	320.7	6.7	1.231906375
18_V15_30_95.FIN2	114.1	0.839	0.3814	0.0097	0.05104	0.00087	0.35746	327.3	7.1	320.9	5.3	368	58	320.9	5.3	1.955392606
18_V15_30_98.FIN2	394	1.512	0.3823	0.0066	0.05118	0.00058	0.39109	328.4	4.8	321.7	3.5	379	37	321.7	3.5	2.040194884
18_V15_30_84.FIN2	99	0.883	0.389	0.013	0.0523	0.0017	0.22562	333.2	9.3	328	11	363	87	328	11	1.56062425
18_V15_30_52.FIN2	168.7	1.241	0.3845	0.0086	0.05234	0.00089	0.40999	329.6	6.3	328.8	5.4	332	50	328.8	5.4	0.242718447
18_V15_30_48.FIN2	137	1.169	0.431	0.011	0.0527	0.001	0.28391	362.9	7.8	332.9	6.1	556	60	332.9	6.1	8.266740149
18_V15_30_33.FIN2	148.4	0.67	0.4098	0.008	0.05491	0.00072	0.27073	348.2	5.8	344.6	4.4	356	46	344.6	4.4	1.03388857
18_V15_30_88.FIN2	46.6	1.118	0.428	0.017	0.05596	0.00099	0.27572	360	12	351.9	6.3	379	77	351.9	6.3	2.25
18_V15_30_35.FIN2	332	1.271	0.4368	0.0089	0.05721	0.0007	0.3654	367.5	6.3	358.6	4.3	407	45	358.6	4.3	2.421768707
18_V15_30_62.FIN2	280	1.81	0.434	0.01	0.0573	0.0011	0.70615	365.6	7.1	359	6.7	403	37	359	6.7	1.805251641
18_V15_30_50.FIN2	235.4	0.839	0.471	0.0093	0.06062	0.00068	0.33016	391.4	6.4	379.3	4.1	450	43	379.3	4.1	3.09146653
18_V15_30_8.FIN2	78.5	0.597	0.507	0.015	0.06149	0.0009	0.36759	415	10	384.6	5.4	560	66	384.6	5.4	7.325301205
18_V15_30_7.FIN2	208	1.039	0.469	0.012	0.0617	0.001	0.077334	390.2	8	385.7	6.3	403	63	385.7	6.3	1.153254741
18_V15_30_111.FIN2	155	1.21	0.466	0.0092	0.06207	0.00054	0.070809	387.7	6.4	388.2	3.3	370	43	388.2	3.3	-0.128965695
18_V15_30_76.FIN2	119.2	1.034	0.491	0.012	0.06333	0.00083	0.33155	404.7	7.9	395.8	5	448	51	395.8	5	2.199159872
18_V15_30_97.FIN2	235	1.084	0.533	0.012	0.06623	0.00076	0.53068	432.8	7.8	413.3	4.6	525	41	413.3	4.6	4.505545287
18_V15_30_46.FIN2	235	0.987	0.5179	0.0098	0.06625	0.00096	0.49743	423.2	6.5	413.5	5.8	475	42	413.5	5.8	2.292060491
18_V15_30_67.FIN2	212	0.744	0.538	0.016	0.0669	0.001	0.38652	435.3	9.8	417.4	6.3	515	51	417.4	6.3	4.112106593
18_V15_30_3.FIN2	267	1.82	0.5192	0.0083	0.06726	0.00081	0.40496	424.2	5.6	419.6	4.9	440	35	419.6	4.9	1.084394154
18_V15_30_106.FIN2	367	4.64	0.538	0.011	0.06736	0.00088	0.40214	436.1	7.5	420.2	5.3	509	36	420.2	5.3	3.645952763
18_V15_30_29.FIN2	465	22.4	0.546	0.02	0.0675	0.002	0.85202	441	13	421	12	538	41	421	12	4.535147392
18_V15_30_102.FIN2	97	0.954	0.527	0.014	0.0677	0.0011	0.55688	428.7	9.2	422.3	6.8	478	53	422.3	6.8	1.492885468
18_V15_30_31.FIN2	149.5	0.818	0.5365	0.0097	0.06787	0.00086	0.2246	436.4	6.6	423.2	5.2	481	45	423.2	5.2	3.024747938
18_V15_30_113.FIN2	197.5	1.08	0.5211	0.008	0.06803	0.00067	0.49605	426.1	5.2	424.2	4.1	432	29	424.2	4.1	0.445904717
18_V15_30_89.FIN2	77.8	1.4	0.519	0.014	0.0681	0.0012	0.44522	423.3	9.2	424.7	7	415	54	424.7	7	-0.330734704
18_V15_30_15.FIN2	123	0.433	0.526	0.012	0.0682	0.0012	0.46503	429.2	7.7	425.4	6.9	422	48	425.4	6.9	0.885368127
18_V15_30_11.FIN2	232.5	0.681	0.5286	0.0094	0.06866	0.00096	0.37098	430.4	6.3	428	5.8	425	41	428	5.8	0.557620818
18_V15_30_73.FIN2	90	1.31	0.527	0.014	0.06868	0.00069	0.197	428.1	9	428.2	4.2	409	56	428.2	4.2	-0.023359028
18_V15_30_55.FIN2	211	0.589	0.55	0.013	0.069	0.0011	0.39195	444.2	8.4	430.1	6.5	511	50	430.1	6.5	3.174245835
18_V15_30_47.FIN2	132.4	0.8074	0.526	0.011	0.06934	0.00086	0.22284	429.8	7.7	432.1	5.2	408	50	432.1	5.2	-0.53513262
18_V15_30_54.FIN2	324	1.263	0.543	0.014	0.0698	0.0016	0.58426	439.9	9.1	434.7	9.7	463	49	434.7	9.7	1.182086838
18_V15_30_85.FIN2	98.7	0.935	0.566	0.013	0.07057	0.00082	0.31901	454.6	8.6	439.6	4.9	517	49	439.6	4.9	3.299604048
18_V15_30_34.FIN2	290	0.738	0.556	0.014	0.0706	0.0017	0.69975	449.7	9.6	440	10	490	42	440	10	2.156993551
18_V15_30_92.FIN2	78.6	1.06	0.554	0.012	0.07192	0.00085	0.089201	447.8	8.2	447.7	5.1	434	54	447.7	5.1	0.022331398
18_V15_30_17.FIN2	416	0.671	0.554	0.011	0.072	0.0011	0.72569	447.5	6.8	447.8	6.9	454	32	447.8	6.9	-0.067039106
18_V15_30_24.FIN2	200.3	0.802	0.591	0.01	0.0721	0.0011	0.60691	470.8	6.5	448.7	6.9	563	32	448.7	6.9	4.694137638
18_V15_30_80.FIN2	75.8	0.636	0.552	0.013	0.07242	0.00099	0.16551	445.3	8.6	450.6	6	411	55	450.6	6	-1.190208848
18_V15_30_10.FIN2	169.6	1.008	0.567	0.011	0.0728	0.0012	0.11706	455.5	7.5	452.8	7.5	467	57	452.8	7.5	0.592755214
18_V15_30_27.FIN2	699	8.93	0.5828	0.0069	0.07423	0.00099	0.43026	466	4.4	461.5	5.9	477	33	461.5	5.9	0.965665236
18_V15_30_90.FIN2	322.2	0.683	0.5871	0.0094	0.07469	0.00087	0.4658	468.7	6	464.3	5.2	490	32	464.3	5.2	0.938766802
18_V15_30_21.FIN2	193	0.785	0.6	0.013	0.0771	0.0015	0.43474	476.4	8.2	478.7	9	442	50	478.7	9	-0.482787573
18_V15_30_1.FIN2	269.9	0.62	0.653	0.014	0.0814	0.0016	0.72466	509.5	8.4	504.3	9.3	527	34	504.3	9.3	1.02060844
18_V15_30_20.FIN2	254	2.2	0.661	0.015	0.0825	0.0013	0.75468	514.1	9	510.9	7.9	511	33	510.9	7.9	0.622446995
18_V15_30_126.FIN2	51.1	0.3827	0.665	0.017	0.08421	0.00092	0.15375	516	11	521.2	5.5	472	58	521.2	5.5	-1.007751938
18_V15_30_63.FIN2	110.4	0.576	0.685	0.015	0.0845	0.0017	0.40458	528.4	9.1	522.4	9.8	564	54	522.4	9.8	1.135503407

18_V15_30_12.FIN2	141.2	0.554	0.675	0.011	0.0845	0.001	0.32671	523.4	6.7	522.6	5.9	513	37	522.6	5.9	0.152846771
18_V15_30_49.FIN2	162	2.87	0.711	0.019	0.088	0.0021	0.65575	544	12	543	12	539	50	543	12	0.183823529
18_V15_30_118.FIN2	110.7	1.419	0.731	0.013	0.09084	0.00093	0.17675	555.9	7.5	560.4	5.5	534	42	560.4	5.5	-0.809498111
18_V15_30_40.FIN2	51.1	0.832	0.767	0.02	0.0936	0.0012	0.23392	576	12	576.9	7	567	60	576.9	7	-0.15625
18_V15_30_123.FIN2	178.6	0.4518	0.787	0.01	0.09542	0.00089	0.22437	589.4	6	587.4	5.2	592	32	587.4	5.2	0.33932813
18_V15_30_2.FIN2	162.9	0.4571	0.812	0.011	0.0982	0.0011	0.2898	602.9	6.4	604	6.5	592	35	604	6.5	-0.182451484
18_V15_30_30.FIN2	305	0.469	0.85	0.011	0.101	0.001	0.44953	625.1	6	620.3	6	618	26	620.3	6	0.76787714
18_V15_30_108.FIN2	158.2	0.781	0.927	0.011	0.10802	0.0009	0.24794	666.3	6	661.1	5.2	673	29	661.1	5.2	0.780429236
18_V15_30_19.FIN2	124.5	0.617	0.956	0.018	0.1096	0.0021	0.52915	680.9	8.9	670	12	693	40	670	12	1.600822441
18_V15_30_61.FIN2	233	1.88	0.952	0.026	0.1112	0.0039	0.65549	677	14	679	23	696	59	679	23	-0.295420975
18_V15_30_43.FIN2	184.6	0.5588	1.002	0.017	0.1133	0.0013	0.39913	704.1	8.4	692	7.3	742	32	692	7.3	1.718505894
18_V15_30_127.FIN2	85.7	0.606	1.075	0.029	0.1181	0.0021	0.58129	739	14	720	12	797	47	720	12	2.571041949
18_V15_30_77.FIN2	146	5.43	1.044	0.022	0.1197	0.002	0.6471	724	11	728	11	732	36	728	11	-0.552486188
18_V15_30_6.FIN2	196.5	3	1.207	0.014	0.1306	0.0013	0.36501	803	6.6	791	7.5	829	26	791	7.5	1.494396015
18_V15_30_32.FIN2	148.5	1.589	1.249	0.03	0.132	0.0025	0.71056	821	14	799	15	879	34	799	15	2.679658952
18_V15_30_104.FIN2	237	5.5	1.45	0.14	0.133	0.0095	0.96923	865	56	799	54	1035	71	799	54	7.630057803
18_V15_30_91.FIN2	31.1	0.876	1.325	0.032	0.1412	0.0016	0.14738	857	14	851.2	9	866	53	851.2	9	0.676779463
18_V15_30_57.FIN2	207	3.39	1.434	0.032	0.1496	0.0025	0.32674	903	13	898	14	910	48	898	14	0.553709856
18_V15_30_100.FIN2	282	2.297	1.459	0.026	0.1502	0.002	0.61578	913	11	902	11	935	26	902	11	1.204819277
18_V15_30_36.FIN2	390	4.78	1.472	0.02	0.1514	0.0023	0.57932	919.2	8.4	909	13	928	27	909	13	1.109660574
18_V15_30_101.FIN2	111.2	0.616	1.47	0.025	0.1515	0.0021	0.55822	918	10	909	12	936	31	909	12	0.980392157
18_V15_30_42.FIN2	75.6	1.082	1.456	0.032	0.1523	0.0026	0.4331	911	13	914	15	900	44	914	15	-0.329308452
18_V15_30_13.FIN2	188	1.37	1.633	0.059	0.165	0.0059	0.92896	978	23	983	33	969	27	983	33	-0.511247444
18_V15_30_115.FIN2	494	3.35	1.621	0.024	0.1649	0.0029	0.74835	977	9.5	983	16	960	24	983	16	-0.614124872
18_V15_30_60.FIN2	248.1	2.91	1.674	0.019	0.1663	0.0022	0.54583	998	7.3	991	12	1014	24	991	12	0.701402806
18_V15_30_110.FIN2	103.9	1.65	1.803	0.029	0.1797	0.0019	0.36364	1045	11	1065	10	995	32	995	10	-1.913875598
18_V15_30_69.FIN2	96.6	0.6736	1.853	0.028	0.178	0.0023	0.4686	1063	10	1055	13	1080	29	1080	29	2.314814815
18_V15_30_28.FIN2	230.6	1.375	2.464	0.032	0.2187	0.003	0.67899	1261.8	9	1274	16	1226	23	1226	23	-3.915171289
18_V15_30_122.FIN2	142	1.095	2.498	0.035	0.2224	0.003	0.727	1270	10	1294	16	1231	20	1231	20	-5.117790414
18_V15_30_71.FIN2	128.3	1.367	2.974	0.043	0.2434	0.0036	0.73639	1400	11	1404	19	1394	21	1394	21	-0.717360115
18_V15_30_41.FIN2	39.2	0.687	2.701	0.05	0.22	0.0035	0.28073	1327	14	1281	18	1398	42	1398	42	8.369098712
18_V15_30_94.FIN2	50	0.956	3.034	0.077	0.2435	0.0046	0.73145	1413	20	1404	24	1430	34	1430	34	1.818181818
18_V15_30_51.FIN2	115.7	0.727	3.195	0.032	0.2526	0.0026	0.47015	1455	7.7	1451	13	1461	21	1461	21	0.684462697
18_V15_30_75.FIN2	371	3.28	3.105	0.068	0.2416	0.0041	0.75303	1430	18	1394	22	1487	31	1487	31	6.254203093
18_V15_30_107.FIN2	243.4	1.87	3.516	0.026	0.2646	0.0018	0.63105	1530.2	5.9	1513.4	9.2	1553	13	1553	13	2.549903413
18_V15_30_81.FIN2	29.4	0.3915	3.542	0.056	0.2665	0.0029	0.35839	1536	12	1523	15	1554	29	1554	29	1.994851995
18_V15_30_37.FIN2	18.75	0.726	4.121	0.074	0.2932	0.0036	0.41999	1655	15	1657	18	1643	32	1643	32	-0.852099817
18_V15_30_64.FIN2	145.9	1.119	4.042	0.058	0.2891	0.004	0.46434	1644	12	1637	20	1647	29	1647	29	0.607164542
18_V15_30_96.FIN2	188	1.408	4.76	0.043	0.3238	0.0026	0.45879	1777.2	7.6	1808	13	1749	17	1749	17	-3.373356204
18_V15_30_68.FIN2	108.1	0.681	4.49	0.12	0.2958	0.0041	0.53885	1724	22	1670	20	1782	39	1782	39	6.285072952
18_V15_30_5.FIN2	113	0.768	4.948	0.054	0.322	0.0029	0.46771	1809.4	9.1	1799	14	1821	19	1821	19	1.208127403
18_V15_30_22.FIN2	19.1	1.115	5.11	0.12	0.3283	0.0072	0.48486	1831	19	1827	35	1822	49	1822	49	-0.27442371
18_V15_30_125.FIN2	52.4	0.778	5.236	0.059	0.3383	0.0026	0.45448	1856.8	9.8	1878	13	1832	19	1832	19	-2.510917031
18_V15_30_66.FIN2	207	1.19	5.221	0.057	0.3359	0.0035	0.67193	1855	9.4	1866	17	1845	15	1845	15	-1.138211382
18_V15_30_120.FIN2	171.9	0.956	5.552	0.057	0.3503	0.0037	0.52888	1907.5	8.9	1935	17	1880	17	1880	17	-2.925531915

18_V15_30_99.FIN2	353.6	5.49	6.021	0.074	0.3702	0.0046	0.63907	1978	11	2030	22	1934	21	1934	21	-4.963805584	
18_V15_30_23.FIN2	70.4	0.717	6.099	0.077	0.3603	0.0041	0.5593	1989	11	1986	20	1982	20	1982	20	-0.201816347	
18_V15_30_14.FIN2	187	2.64	7.789	0.085	0.4139	0.0049	0.51495	2205.9	9.8	2232	22	2167	20	2167	20	-2.999538533	
18_V15_30_112.FIN2	125	1.011	9.549	0.096	0.4702	0.0049	0.59382	2391.3	9.2	2484	21	2312	16	2312	16	-7.439446367	
18_V15_30_9.FIN2	66.4	0.822	11.55	0.19	0.4921	0.0081	0.56073	2566	15	2577	35	2548	27	2548	27	-1.138147567	
sample 15AP30	coordinates	80°06' 13.9"															
		057°53' 02.1"															
								207/235		206/238		207/206			Best age		
Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	Age Ma	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	(Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*	
15AP30_21.FIN2	2409	34.4	0.3054	0.0095	0.0408	0.0014	0.68581	270.3	7.4	257.9	8.9	354	65	257.9	8.9	4.587495376	
15AP30_34.FIN2	152.6	1.156	0.3088	0.0094	0.04242	0.00094	0.25401	273.3	7.2	267.7	5.8	296	69	267.7	5.8	2.04903037	
15AP30_128.FIN2	126	1.617	0.3145	0.0095	0.04306	0.00058	0.17028	278.8	7.3	271.8	3.6	327	67	271.8	3.6	2.510760402	
15AP30_41.FIN2	289	3.29	0.324	0.018	0.0437	0.0023	0.55982	284	14	276	14	340	100	276	14	2.816901408	
15AP30_74.FIN2	483	1.561	0.3214	0.0046	0.04462	0.0004	0.35451	282.8	3.5	281.4	2.4	284	33	281.4	2.4	0.495049505	
15AP30_117.FIN2	341	1.43	0.3395	0.0089	0.04576	0.00087	0.39866	296.3	6.7	288.4	5.3	380	54	288.4	5.3	2.666216672	
15AP30_63.FIN2	328.7	1.383	0.3257	0.0059	0.04587	0.00047	0.26787	286.4	4.5	289.1	2.9	277	41	289.1	2.9	0.94273743	
15AP30_33.FIN2	347	0.869	0.3562	0.008	0.04613	0.00088	0.32099	309.1	6	291.4	5.6	478	53	291.4	5.6	5.726302168	
15AP30_127.FIN2	258	2.62	0.3455	0.0062	0.04755	0.00048	0.35242	301	4.7	299.4	3	291	40	299.4	3	0.531561462	
15AP30_68.FIN2	82.4	0.784	0.355	0.012	0.04857	0.0008	0.14807	307.6	8.7	305.7	4.9	318	79	305.7	4.9	0.617685306	
15AP30_89.FIN2	748	1.413	0.3425	0.0057	0.04879	0.00052	0.47094	299.7	4.3	307.1	3.2	257	31	307.1	3.2	2.469135802	
15AP30_83.FIN2	262	2.28	0.3565	0.0088	0.04889	0.00053	0.24129	309	6.6	307.7	3.2	328	53	307.7	3.2	0.420711974	
15AP30_82.FIN2	232	1.01	0.374	0.015	0.049	0.0012	0.50218	322	11	308.6	7.1	445	79	308.6	7.1	4.161490683	
15AP30_102.FIN2	623	0.973	0.3647	0.0048	0.04936	0.00063	0.4806	315.5	3.6	310.5	3.8	375	29	310.5	3.8	1.584786054	
15AP30_55.FIN2	219	2.636	0.386	0.01	0.04996	0.00053	0.16927	330.8	7.6	314.2	3.3	460	63	314.2	3.3	5.018137848	
15AP30_90.FIN2	89.1	1.901	0.371	0.012	0.05014	0.00084	0.13572	319.5	9	315.3	5.1	345	71	315.3	5.1	1.314553991	
15AP30_3.FIN2	151	1.405	0.408	0.013	0.05017	0.00085	0.38632	347.7	9	315.5	5.2	550	58	315.5	5.2	9.260857061	
15AP30_15.FIN2	522.9	0.682	0.3685	0.0086	0.05054	0.0008	0.18821	318.4	6.3	317.8	4.9	331	55	317.8	4.9	0.188442211	
15AP30_9.FIN2	485	2.03	0.376	0.0066	0.0506	0.0006	0.41435	324.3	4.8	318.2	3.7	358	40	318.2	3.7	1.880974406	
15AP30_29.FIN2	81.8	2.413	0.414	0.012	0.05169	0.00092	0.16338	351.8	8.6	324.8	5.6	515	70	324.8	5.6	7.674815236	
15AP30_92.FIN2	73	2.13	0.395	0.017	0.0524	0.0012	0.24332	337	12	329.3	7.2	396	86	329.3	7.2	2.284866469	
15AP30_14.FIN2	94.4	2.247	0.382	0.016	0.0526	0.0012	0.48071	327	12	330.2	7.2	311	84	330.2	7.2	0.978593272	
15AP30_110.FIN2	92.7	2.261	0.3965	0.0093	0.05287	0.00079	0.029454	338.5	6.7	332.1	4.8	375	61	332.1	4.8	1.890694239	
15AP30_85.FIN2	927	1.884	0.3846	0.005	0.05365	0.00059	0.29798	330.2	3.7	337.2	3.6	303	34	337.2	3.6	2.119927317	
15AP30_36.FIN2	87.9	2.59	0.443	0.015	0.05383	0.0009	0.26506	372	11	337.9	5.5	512	71	337.9	5.5	9.166666667	
15AP30_4.FIN2	375	1.738	0.3956	0.006	0.05393	0.00059	0.39912	338.2	4.4	338.6	3.6	332	33	338.6	3.6	0.118273211	
15AP30_31.FIN2	235	1.419	0.405	0.014	0.054	0.0011	0.15462	345	10	338.7	6.7	370	77	338.7	6.7	1.826086957	
15AP30_28.FIN2	362	1.186	0.3952	0.0082	0.05404	0.00099	0.48216	337.8	5.9	339.2	6.1	350	40	339.2	6.1	0.414446418	
15AP30_51.FIN2	164.1	1.3	0.4	0.012	0.05408	0.00087	0.44709	341.2	8.5	339.5	5.3	344	60	339.5	5.3	0.498241501	
15AP30_40.FIN2	115.6	1.81	0.404	0.013	0.05416	0.00096	0.21933	345.3	9.2	340.6	6	331	67	340.6	6	1.361135245	
15AP30_52.FIN2	358	6.24	0.4192	0.0081	0.05463	0.00072	0.33602	356.3	5.6	342.9	4.4	443	45	342.9	4.4	3.760875667	
15AP30_109.FIN2	937	15.17	0.4077	0.006	0.05474	0.00074	0.3359	346.9	4.3	343.5	4.5	365	39	343.5	4.5	0.980109542	
15AP30_113.FIN2	284	2.514	0.4115	0.0084	0.0549	0.00059	0.11461	350.2	5.9	344.5	3.6	384	49	344.5	3.6	1.627641348	
15AP30_10.FIN2	175	1.447	0.416	0.01	0.0553	0.0011	0.44075	352.3	7.4	346.8	7	381	56	346.8	7	1.561169458	
15AP30_48.FIN2	433	4.56	0.417	0.0088	0.0557	0.001	0.53664	353.5	6.3	349.1	6.3	401	47	349.1	6.3	1.244695898	
15AP30_20.FIN2	125.3	1.417	0.424	0.012	0.05703	0.00087	0.15911	359	8.4	357.5	5.3	388	68	357.5	5.3	0.417827298	

15AP30_58.FIN2	101.1	1.648	0.423	0.016	0.0572	0.0011	0.31203	359	11	358.4	6.4	352	79	358.4	6.4	0.167130919
15AP30_101.FIN2	193	1.365	0.4251	0.0091	0.0577	0.00058	0.20636	360.5	6.5	361.6	3.6	351	48	361.6	3.6	0.305131761
15AP30_112.FIN2	169.5	1.169	0.4356	0.0096	0.05798	0.0006	0.32343	366.4	6.8	363.3	3.6	365	49	363.3	3.6	0.846069869
15AP30_73.FIN2	96	1.754	0.441	0.011	0.0582	0.00064	0.094482	369.9	7.7	364.6	3.9	390	59	364.6	3.9	1.432819681
15AP30_57.FIN2	359	1.145	0.4525	0.0076	0.06075	0.00077	0.17314	380.1	5.3	380.1	4.7	347	44	380.1	4.7	0
15AP30_96.FIN2	256.4	1.362	0.4507	0.0082	0.06112	0.00065	0.15721	377.4	5.7	382.4	3.9	337	45	382.4	3.9	1.324854266
15AP30_38.FIN2	94.3	2.362	0.476	0.021	0.0624	0.0022	0.34112	394	14	390	13	450	110	390	13	1.015228426
15AP30_49.FIN2	220.1	1.77	0.471	0.01	0.06248	0.00087	0.24462	391.6	7	390.7	5.3	373	52	390.7	5.3	0.229826353
15AP30_59.FIN2	202.9	1.588	0.48	0.011	0.06276	0.00069	0.23808	398.1	7.3	392.4	4.2	411	49	392.4	4.2	1.431801055
15AP30_35.FIN2	370	4.82	0.499	0.013	0.0636	0.0013	0.11352	410	8.5	397.6	7.9	448	59	397.6	7.9	3.024390244
15AP30_87.FIN2	101.8	0.862	0.51	0.017	0.0648	0.001	0.12244	419	11	404.9	6.3	489	77	404.9	6.3	3.365155131
15AP30_95.FIN2	136.2	0.973	0.509	0.011	0.06723	0.00092	0.3221	418.8	7.5	419.4	5.6	392	47	419.4	5.6	0.143266476
15AP30_42.FIN2	1858	7.08	0.538	0.0096	0.0681	0.0013	0.55773	436.8	6.3	424.4	8	513	36	424.4	8	2.838827839
15AP30_27.FIN2	149.7	0.526	0.532	0.011	0.06989	0.00087	0.14636	433.1	7.5	435.4	5.2	406	53	435.4	5.2	0.531055184
15AP30_99.FIN2	202.8	2.04	0.599	0.018	0.0713	0.0021	0.21449	479	12	444	13	596	70	444	13	7.306889353
15AP30_46.FIN2	728	1.608	0.568	0.011	0.0719	0.0011	0.27465	456.2	7.1	447.8	6.8	508	45	447.8	6.8	1.841297676
15AP30_72.FIN2	145.3	1.442	0.555	0.01	0.07279	0.00072	0.033222	448.3	6.9	452.9	4.3	434	46	452.9	4.3	1.026098595
15AP30_86.FIN2	418	0.944	0.566	0.01	0.0729	0.0011	0.47609	454.6	6.8	453.3	6.3	484	43	453.3	6.3	0.285965684
15AP30_66.FIN2	515	2.212	0.5784	0.009	0.0742	0.001	0.37646	463.5	5.8	461.5	6.1	458	34	461.5	6.1	0.431499461
15AP30_61.FIN2	229	1.293	0.614	0.013	0.0769	0.0011	0.47304	485	8.1	477.7	6.5	523	42	477.7	6.5	1.505154639
15AP30_56.FIN2	393	3.369	0.6145	0.0078	0.0789	0.00069	0.28183	486.5	5	489.5	4.1	471	31	489.5	4.1	0.616649538
15AP30_94.FIN2	633	4.04	0.6186	0.0071	0.07904	0.00065	0.44024	488.7	4.5	490.4	3.9	486	23	490.4	3.9	0.347861674
15AP30_93.FIN2	160.2	2.017	0.671	0.011	0.08312	0.00079	0.15513	520.5	6.9	514.6	4.7	550	41	514.6	4.7	1.133525456
15AP30_105.FIN2	182	1.237	0.682	0.015	0.0834	0.0013	0.2328	528.9	9.3	517.4	7.7	590	51	517.4	7.7	2.174324069
15AP30_114.FIN2	80.4	0.689	0.683	0.017	0.08446	0.00098	0.022413	527	10	522.6	5.8	526	56	522.6	5.8	0.834914611
15AP30_118.FIN2	765	1.166	0.705	0.01	0.0869	0.0012	0.46847	541.1	6.1	537.2	6.9	554	29	537.2	6.9	0.72075402
15AP30_75.FIN2	122.6	1.047	0.755	0.017	0.0904	0.0015	0.1215	569.7	9.8	557.6	8.7	621	55	557.6	8.7	2.123924873
15AP30_23.FIN2	405	1.896	0.766	0.01	0.09255	0.00099	0.14695	577	5.9	570.5	5.8	604	28	570.5	5.8	1.126516464
15AP30_106.FIN2	50.8	1.058	0.875	0.033	0.1039	0.0018	0.38499	640	17	637	11	654	76	637	11	0.46875
15AP30_103.FIN2	234	1.105	1.134	0.029	0.1157	0.0021	0.33745	769	14	706	12	958	51	706	12	8.192457737
15AP30_1.FIN2	86.2	1.017	1.097	0.027	0.1217	0.0029	0.52187	750	13	740	17	805	56	740	17	1.333333333
15AP30_123.FIN2	711.3	1.022	1.184	0.019	0.1259	0.0018	0.29203	792.7	8.9	764	10	865	35	764	10	3.620537404
15AP30_97.FIN2	106	0.85	1.252	0.049	0.1349	0.0028	0.56154	820	22	816	16	840	65	816	16	0.487804878
15AP30_37.FIN2	91.7	1.786	1.499	0.035	0.1491	0.0018	0.22894	928	14	895.9	9.8	1004	49	895.9	9.8	3.459051724
15AP30_121.FIN2	310	1.346	1.699	0.023	0.1748	0.0022	0.51535	1007.3	8.5	1038	12	948	28	948	12	3.047751415
15AP30_108.FIN2	452	1.538	1.781	0.021	0.1747	0.0017	0.61941	1038	7.5	1037.6	9.5	1034	20	1034	20	0.348162476
15AP30_120.FIN2	179	0.754	1.857	0.026	0.1798	0.0021	0.41847	1064.7	9.2	1065	11	1056	30	1056	30	0.852272727
15AP30_8.FIN2	112.7	1.757	2.11	0.029	0.1962	0.0024	0.31894	1152.3	9.5	1155	13	1158	28	1158	28	0.259067358
15AP30_116.FIN2	140.5	5.13	2.06	0.032	0.1871	0.0026	0.38981	1135	11	1105	14	1182	32	1182	32	6.514382403
15AP30_124.FIN2	309.4	1.452	2.329	0.038	0.2056	0.0039	0.37235	1219	12	1204	21	1236	40	1236	40	2.588996764
15AP30_79.FIN2	261	1.913	2.881	0.035	0.2379	0.0024	0.70992	1375.8	9.1	1376	13	1381	18	1381	18	0.362056481
15AP30_30.FIN2	157	2.233	3.047	0.049	0.2453	0.0035	0.54625	1419	12	1414	18	1415	27	1415	27	0.070671378
15AP30_11.FIN2	80.3	0.608	2.712	0.06	0.2174	0.0025	0.46134	1329	17	1268	13	1432	41	1432	41	11.45251397
15AP30_80.FIN2	256	1.648	3.248	0.031	0.2567	0.0022	0.55041	1468.9	7.3	1473	11	1467	17	1467	17	0.408997955
15AP30_67.FIN2	169.5	2.68	3.202	0.067	0.2465	0.0052	0.54682	1456	16	1424	26	1498	41	1498	41	4.939919893

15AP30_115.FIN2	29.7	0.91	3.332	0.083	0.253	0.0037	0.38353	1485	19	1453	19	1536	43	1536	43	5.403645833	
15AP30_43.FIN2	276.9	2.116	3.81	0.11	0.2785	0.0095	0.62411	1603	24	1581	48	1604	48	1604	48	1.433915212	
15AP30_45.FIN2	305.2	2.79	3.515	0.061	0.2587	0.0047	0.63169	1531	14	1482	24	1620	27	1620	27	8.518518519	
15AP30_107.FIN2	534	2.291	3.69	0.056	0.2666	0.0047	0.61399	1568	12	1523	24	1633	26	1633	26	6.736068585	
15AP30_39.FIN2	56.2	2.88	4.2	0.17	0.304	0.013	0.58951	1676	34	1705	65	1658	81	1658	81	2.834740651	
15AP30_104.FIN2	205.2	1.77	4.246	0.054	0.2975	0.0031	0.64148	1681	11	1679	15	1685	19	1685	19	0.356083086	
15AP30_25.FIN2	193.1	1.879	4.571	0.071	0.3128	0.0045	0.45446	1743	13	1754	22	1719	25	1719	25	2.036067481	
15AP30_130.FIN2	236.8	1.497	3.669	0.099	0.2533	0.0077	0.57984	1564	21	1459	41	1728	48	1728	48	15.56712963	
15AP30_100.FIN2	203	1.854	4.545	0.072	0.3104	0.0039	0.73023	1740	13	1742	19	1743	19	1743	19	0.057372347	
15AP30_5.FIN2	374	2.402	4.726	0.041	0.32	0.0027	0.46556	1772.6	7.2	1791	13	1755	15	1755	15	2.051282051	
15AP30_13.FIN2	34.8	0.99	4.891	0.082	0.3235	0.004	0.2782	1801	14	1806	19	1796	32	1796	32	0.556792873	
15AP30_60.FIN2	216	1.04	4.8	0.046	0.3145	0.0027	0.46755	1784.1	8.1	1762	13	1800	16	1800	16	2.111111111	
15AP30_78.FIN2	55.4	0.938	4.892	0.069	0.3214	0.0031	0.30558	1800	12	1796	15	1801	26	1801	26	0.277623542	
15AP30_77.FIN2	24.98	0.219	5.27	0.15	0.343	0.011	0.34614	1859	25	1898	51	1831	67	1831	67	3.659202622	
15AP30_62.FIN2	9.81	0.3745	5.21	0.15	0.3338	0.0059	0.25567	1852	24	1855	28	1836	53	1836	53	1.034858388	
15AP30_26.FIN2	11.24	0.418	5.35	0.18	0.3438	0.0084	0.38679	1868	28	1910	39	1840	56	1840	56	3.804347826	
15AP30_19.FIN2	15.18	0.3362	5.51	0.18	0.3491	0.0089	0.47748	1901	29	1934	44	1861	49	1861	49	3.922622246	
15AP30_17.FIN2	13.54	0.1872	5.5	0.14	0.348	0.0062	0.36276	1902	22	1927	29	1880	44	1880	44	2.5	
15AP30_54.FIN2	31.37	0.357	5.33	0.11	0.3356	0.0061	0.26901	1881	18	1864	29	1895	41	1895	41	1.635883905	
15AP30_119.FIN2	37.5	1.17	5.29	0.17	0.328	0.011	0.52143	1869	30	1828	54	1906	56	1906	56	4.092339979	
15AP30_24.FIN2	72.7	0.695	5.19	0.12	0.3206	0.008	0.67793	1846	20	1794	38	1914	37	1914	37	6.269592476	
15AP30_18.FIN2	19	0.391	5.53	0.16	0.3399	0.0064	0.43939	1901	25	1885	30	1937	49	1937	49	2.684563758	
15AP30_91.FIN2	14.2	0.292	5.63	0.14	0.3356	0.0063	0.1496	1923	21	1864	30	1944	52	1944	52	4.115226337	
15AP30_12.FIN2	9.1	0.334	5.84	0.21	0.3515	0.0089	0.13342	1956	33	1948	40	1969	81	1969	81	1.066531234	
15AP30_64.FIN2	12.81	0.2966	5.67	0.14	0.3461	0.0065	0.35204	1939	20	1914	31	1976	44	1976	44	3.137651822	
15AP30_65.FIN2	139.8	0.64	5.84	0.21	0.334	0.012	0.67441	1943	32	1854	56	2042	54	2042	54	9.206660137	
15AP30_126.FIN2	110.7	0.281	5.39	0.12	0.3082	0.0078	0.65693	1882	19	1730	38	2053	35	2053	35	15.73307355	
15AP30_76.FIN2	161.3	0.6241	6.48	0.11	0.3667	0.0067	0.61039	2042	15	2015	31	2079	27	2079	27	3.078403078	
15AP30_122.FIN2	32.95	0.1484	7.43	0.19	0.3853	0.0047	0.3163	2158	22	2100	22	2206	40	2206	40	4.805077063	
15AP30_69.FIN2	687	3.2	9.81	0.14	0.4569	0.0059	0.62845	2419	13	2424	26	2417	17	2417	17	0.289615225	
15AP30_47.FIN2	576	11.98	10.13	0.16	0.4435	0.0073	0.61313	2446	15	2364	32	2512	24	2512	24	5.891719745	
15AP30_71.FIN2	82.7	0.8813	11.25	0.11	0.4605	0.0038	0.43643	2547.2	9.7	2441	17	2630	17	2630	17	7.186311787	
15AP30_53.FIN2	25.7	0.595	11.07	0.33	0.439	0.0096	0.36742	2528	29	2342	43	2646	48	2646	48	11.48904006	
15AP30_22.FIN2	198.6	0.63	10.06	0.35	0.3983	0.0063	0.7463	2435	32	2161	29	2666	42	2666	42	18.94223556	
15AP30_129.FIN2	121.8	0.463	70.7	3.7	0.781	0.028	0.86973	4331	57	3710	100	4608	41	4608	41	19.48784722	
sample 15AP27	coordinates	80°05' 52.2"															
		057°52' 56.8"															
								207/235		206/238		207/206		Best age			
Grain #	[U] ppm	U/Th	207/235	2σ error	206/238	2σ error	RHO	Age Ma	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	Age (Ma)	2σ error	(Ma)	2σ error	% Discordance*	
15AP27_62.FIN2	249	1.533	0.249	0.0061	0.03595	0.00046	0.38694	226.5	5.1	227.7	2.8	229	53	227.7	2.8	0.529801325	
15AP27_15.FIN2	167.9	1.052	0.268	0.01	0.0379	0.0012	0.31185	240.3	8.3	239.9	7.5	235	78	239.9	7.5	0.166458593	
15AP27_112.FIN2	544	1.81	0.289	0.0063	0.04007	0.00093	0.49735	257.4	4.9	253.2	5.7	298	50	253.2	5.7	1.631701632	
15AP27_128.FIN2	210.1	2.081	0.2959	0.0072	0.04065	0.00082	0.3433	264.2	5.5	256.8	5.1	359	59	256.8	5.1	2.800908403	
15AP27_18.FIN2	49.1	3.448	0.299	0.014	0.0415	0.0012	0.13316	264	11	262.2	7.5	271	99	262.2	7.5	0.681818182	
15AP27_117.FIN2	132	1.002	0.3124	0.0091	0.0431	0.00072	0.23006	276.1	7.1	272	4.4	283	63	272	4.4	1.484969214	

15AP27_34.FIN2	47	0.55	0.319	0.013	0.04358	0.0007	0.20937	281	11	275.4	4.3	317	85	275.4	4.3	1.992882562
15AP27_7.FIN2	595	147.4	0.322	0.0063	0.04461	0.00079	0.52206	283.1	4.8	281.3	4.9	291	40	281.3	4.9	0.635817732
15AP27_53.FIN2	402	1.25	0.325	0.0076	0.04462	0.0008	0.18656	287	5.8	281.4	4.9	324	60	281.4	4.9	1.951219512
15AP27_17.FIN2	124.6	1.558	0.325	0.011	0.0456	0.0013	0.48783	285	8.7	287.1	7.7	284	67	287.1	7.7	0.736842105
15AP27_113.FIN2	172	2.22	0.3439	0.009	0.04569	0.00071	0.35456	299.4	6.8	288.5	4.4	374	58	288.5	4.4	3.640614562
15AP27_38.FIN2	269.4	0.769	0.3278	0.0089	0.046	0.001	0.64034	287.9	6.9	290.1	6.3	239	50	290.1	6.3	0.76415422
15AP27_59.FIN2	430	1.276	0.3383	0.0073	0.04634	0.0007	0.37801	295.5	5.5	291.9	4.3	318	46	291.9	4.3	1.218274112
15AP27_36.FIN2	170.5	2.445	0.341	0.011	0.0464	0.0012	0.46885	297.2	8.7	292.4	7.2	269	70	292.4	7.2	1.615074024
15AP27_55.FIN2	586	2.318	0.3463	0.0079	0.04724	0.00097	0.68959	301.5	6	297.5	6	367	39	297.5	6	1.326699834
15AP27_11.FIN2	203.6	1.791	0.342	0.012	0.0475	0.0017	0.45687	297.3	9	299	10	269	74	299	10	0.571812984
15AP27_28.FIN2	360	0.974	0.3511	0.0064	0.04809	0.00072	0.40265	305.1	4.8	302.7	4.5	315	43	302.7	4.5	0.786627335
15AP27_41.FIN2	270	1.284	0.3557	0.0095	0.0481	0.0011	0.53092	308.3	7.1	302.9	6.6	348	52	302.9	6.6	1.751540707
15AP27_130.FIN2	378.7	2.267	0.352	0.007	0.04808	0.00071	0.37793	306.4	5.1	303.2	4.4	312	47	303.2	4.4	1.044386423
15AP27_106.FIN2	87.2	1.027	0.368	0.012	0.04821	0.00077	0.072862	317.5	9.2	303.5	4.7	415	79	303.5	4.7	4.409448819
15AP27_56.FIN2	235	1.35	0.3541	0.0089	0.04847	0.00062	0.17434	307.9	6.6	305.1	3.8	331	56	305.1	3.8	0.909386164
15AP27_118.FIN2	319	1.202	0.3687	0.0082	0.04884	0.00063	0.28005	318.4	6.1	307.3	3.9	382	51	307.3	3.9	3.486180905
15AP27_122.FIN2	656	3.76	0.3685	0.0069	0.04948	0.00074	0.34721	318.3	5.1	311.3	4.6	337	49	311.3	4.6	2.199183161
15AP27_70.FIN2	92.4	3.044	0.361	0.011	0.05027	0.00063	0.10209	311.9	8	316.1	3.9	272	64	316.1	3.9	1.346585444
15AP27_48.FIN2	220.8	1.752	0.3737	0.0082	0.05038	0.0007	0.44077	322.6	5.9	316.8	4.3	347	46	316.8	4.3	1.797892126
15AP27_26.FIN2	145	1.627	0.402	0.014	0.0512	0.0016	0.29712	342.1	9.8	321.9	9.6	406	84	321.9	9.6	5.904706226
15AP27_66.FIN2	313	0.668	0.3814	0.0069	0.05175	0.00057	0.30165	328.2	5.2	325.2	3.5	354	38	325.2	3.5	0.914076782
15AP27_68.FIN2	61.3	1.2	0.395	0.014	0.05229	0.00097	0.19402	338	11	328.5	5.9	403	82	328.5	5.9	2.810650888
15AP27_51.FIN2	178	1.923	0.388	0.023	0.0531	0.0032	0.15596	330	17	333	19	330	130	333	19	0.909090909
15AP27_23.FIN2	91	2.99	0.422	0.03	0.0532	0.0033	0.49059	352	21	334	20	420	130	334	20	5.113636364
15AP27_60.FIN2	152.6	3.501	0.392	0.012	0.0538	0.001	0.46268	334.9	8.4	337.8	6.3	303	59	337.8	6.3	0.865930128
15AP27_31.FIN2	70.8	1.573	0.428	0.018	0.0552	0.0017	0.42138	362	13	346	10	469	93	346	10	4.419889503
15AP27_125.FIN2	118.9	1.213	0.4084	0.0094	0.05594	0.00071	0.082393	347.9	6.7	350.8	4.3	296	57	350.8	4.3	0.833572866
15AP27_76.FIN2	144	0.869	0.442	0.014	0.05693	0.00084	0.13725	372	10	356.9	5.1	472	70	356.9	5.1	4.059139785
15AP27_89.FIN2	177.5	1.104	0.423	0.011	0.0569	0.0011	0.16237	357.1	7.6	356.9	6.5	363	54	356.9	6.5	0.056006721
15AP27_92.FIN2	233.6	1.711	0.4368	0.0089	0.05823	0.00066	0.13859	367.3	6.3	364.8	4	377	47	364.8	4	0.680642527
15AP27_47.FIN2	112	7.8	0.435	0.012	0.0584	0.001	0.33581	367.1	8.3	365.8	6.2	358	62	365.8	6.2	0.354126941
15AP27_43.FIN2	257	1.58	0.44	0.01	0.05864	0.00082	0.41801	370.1	7	367.3	5	358	46	367.3	5	0.756552283
15AP27_119.FIN2	242.7	1.649	0.461	0.011	0.0608	0.0012	0.2107	384.3	8	380.7	7.5	399	66	380.7	7.5	0.93676815
15AP27_10.FIN2	137.3	0.877	0.507	0.014	0.0623	0.0014	0.34674	415.5	9.6	389.7	8.3	552	61	389.7	8.3	6.209386282
15AP27_12.FIN2	128.6	1.444	0.539	0.028	0.0639	0.0017	0.41079	438	19	399	10	629	93	399	10	8.904109589
15AP27_9.FIN2	171.2	3.32	0.486	0.019	0.0641	0.0023	0.57863	401	13	400	14	406	78	400	14	0.249376559
15AP27_33.FIN2	353	103.8	0.485	0.01	0.0646	0.0013	0.36663	400.7	7.1	403.5	7.8	396	56	403.5	7.8	0.69877714
15AP27_14.FIN2	476	1.579	0.492	0.016	0.0648	0.002	0.58545	407	12	404	12	409	68	404	12	0.737100737
15AP27_49.FIN2	81	1.622	0.503	0.018	0.0652	0.0016	0.36172	415	12	407.2	9.4	438	75	407.2	9.4	1.879518072
15AP27_123.FIN2	211.8	1.683	0.525	0.01	0.06562	0.00078	0.40692	428.6	6.9	409.6	4.7	533	39	409.6	4.7	4.433037797
15AP27_32.FIN2	176.7	1.715	0.495	0.012	0.0657	0.0011	0.43927	407.5	8.1	410.1	6.8	389	52	410.1	6.8	0.63803681
15AP27_29.FIN2	215	1.936	0.51	0.011	0.0659	0.0012	0.43994	418.4	7.4	411.3	7.2	431	50	411.3	7.2	1.696940727
15AP27_46.FIN2	451	1.333	0.5246	0.0081	0.06754	0.00082	0.58555	427.7	5.4	421.3	5	461	27	421.3	5	1.496375964
15AP27_4.FIN2	598	5.62	0.556	0.021	0.0676	0.0026	0.51387	448	13	424	15	550	81	424	15	5.357142857
15AP27_126.FIN2	326	3.478	0.535	0.014	0.0685	0.0013	0.43388	434.1	8.9	427.1	8	452	48	427.1	8	1.612531675

15AP27_16.FIN2	151	2.302	0.562	0.021	0.069	0.0025	0.54901	453	14	430	15	590	79	430	15	5.077262693
15AP27_77.FIN2	418	1.67	0.543	0.0094	0.0694	0.0014	0.50791	439.9	6.2	432.5	8.3	478	42	432.5	8.3	1.6822005
15AP27_2.FIN2	244.6	2.085	0.564	0.018	0.0702	0.0029	0.51431	452	12	436	17	509	77	436	17	3.539823009
15AP27_90.FIN2	263.6	1.357	0.543	0.011	0.07145	0.00083	0.29549	439.7	7.2	444.8	5	436	43	444.8	5	1.159881738
15AP27_79.FIN2	184.2	1.109	0.541	0.01	0.07157	0.00081	0.3263	438.6	6.8	445.6	4.9	409	39	445.6	4.9	1.595987232
15AP27_115.FIN2	425	1.28	0.5568	0.0071	0.07226	0.0006	0.39146	449.1	4.6	449.7	3.6	433	30	449.7	3.6	0.133600534
15AP27_81.FIN2	641	3.29	0.5665	0.0093	0.0725	0.0012	0.49172	455.2	6	451.2	7.2	473	39	451.2	7.2	0.878734622
15AP27_6.FIN2	1386	15.49	0.58	0.012	0.0733	0.0015	0.50041	463.9	7.5	455.6	9.2	487	44	455.6	9.2	1.789178702
15AP27_8.FIN2	274.8	2.207	0.625	0.019	0.0748	0.0017	0.59504	491	12	465	10	554	57	465	10	5.295315682
15AP27_95.FIN2	205	1.283	0.578	0.012	0.0752	0.0014	0.45733	462.7	7.8	468.5	8.2	397	43	468.5	8.2	1.253511995
15AP27_44.FIN2	102.6	1.554	0.649	0.025	0.0773	0.0021	0.49848	509	16	480	12	628	77	480	12	5.697445972
15AP27_50.FIN2	356	1.575	0.615	0.016	0.0779	0.0024	0.47679	487.7	9.9	483	14	497	62	483	14	0.963707197
15AP27_108.FIN2	722	3.146	0.649	0.017	0.0802	0.0014	0.26211	506.8	9.9	497.3	8.2	526	52	497.3	8.2	1.874506709
15AP27_126.FIN2	35.6	64	0.902	0.09	0.0982	0.0034	0.030959	643	40	603	20	730	160	603	20	6.220839813
15AP27_69.FIN2	77.2	1.051	0.826	0.019	0.0989	0.0013	0.32219	612	11	607.7	7.4	626	51	607.7	7.4	0.702614379
15AP27_20.FIN2	212.2	3.68	0.867	0.043	0.1004	0.0046	0.61442	634	24	616	27	648	88	616	27	2.839116719
15AP27_3.FIN2	380	3.2	1.122	0.033	0.1201	0.0031	0.63955	763	16	730	18	834	47	730	18	4.325032765
15AP27_54.FIN2	45.3	1.115	1.089	0.033	0.1223	0.0018	0.10374	746	16	744	10	784	66	744	10	0.268096515
15AP27_111.FIN2	58.6	0.882	1.168	0.039	0.1297	0.0036	0.40144	787	18	787	21	779	73	787	21	0
15AP27_88.FIN2	352	1.672	1.225	0.03	0.1311	0.0035	0.62515	811	14	793	20	869	48	793	20	2.219482121
15AP27_40.FIN2	241.2	0.972	1.247	0.034	0.1342	0.0027	0.23002	821	16	811	15	829	62	811	15	1.218026797
15AP27_110.FIN2	749	2.442	1.222	0.013	0.1343	0.0015	0.60913	810.4	6	813.5	8.6	809	19	813.5	8.6	0.382527147
15AP27_91.FIN2	299	1.152	1.267	0.017	0.1387	0.0014	0.43773	830.2	7.5	837.2	8.2	796	27	837.2	8.2	0.84317032
15AP27_109.FIN2	314	3.159	1.38	0.018	0.1455	0.0018	0.44636	879.6	7.8	875.6	9.9	890	28	875.6	9.9	0.45475216
15AP27_57.FIN2	37.3	2.532	1.431	0.041	0.1485	0.0032	0.47094	899	17	892	18	927	55	892	18	0.778642937
15AP27_73.FIN2	162.7	1.247	1.621	0.038	0.155	0.0023	0.58386	977	15	929	13	1110	45	929	13	4.912998976
15AP27_39.FIN2	17.68	0.413	1.573	0.068	0.1556	0.0044	0.38869	957	26	931	24	1058	85	931	24	2.716823406
15AP27_78.FIN2	821	93.5	1.498	0.018	0.1575	0.0018	0.49355	929	7.4	943	10	896	25	943	10	1.506996771
15AP27_129.FIN2	200.3	8.41	1.601	0.033	0.1616	0.0028	0.46665	971	13	966	16	1004	38	966	16	0.514933059
15AP27_83.FIN2	67.6	0.636	1.634	0.034	0.1643	0.0023	0.42763	982	13	980	13	984	39	980	13	0.203665988
15AP27_82.FIN2	232	1.288	1.608	0.025	0.1648	0.0018	0.53233	974.3	9.5	983.2	9.7	940	28	983.2	9.7	0.913476342
15AP27_61.FIN2	118.4	0.635	1.63	0.025	0.1671	0.0023	0.16416	982.1	9.8	996	13	974	41	996	13	1.415334487
15AP27_22.FIN2	77.2	0.781	1.758	0.072	0.1736	0.0064	0.51687	1035	26	1030	35	1012	78	1012	78	1.778656126
15AP27_100.FIN2	214	2.92	1.749	0.025	0.1717	0.0029	0.52089	1025.9	9.3	1021	16	1028	32	1028	32	0.680933852
15AP27_74.FIN2	496	3.5	1.72	0.03	0.1698	0.0034	0.7412	1015	11	1011	19	1032	27	1032	27	2.034883721
15AP27_27.FIN2	236	3.78	2.063	0.042	0.1921	0.0041	0.66422	1136	14	1132	22	1137	36	1137	36	0.439753738
15AP27_42.FIN2	169	2.198	2.172	0.041	0.2005	0.0029	0.55668	1173	14	1178	16	1153	33	1153	33	2.168256722
15AP27_87.FIN2	206	3.18	2.064	0.063	0.1921	0.0056	0.36927	1135	20	1131	30	1168	52	1168	52	3.167808219
15AP27_99.FIN2	491	1.643	2.659	0.027	0.2298	0.0023	0.76482	1317.5	7.8	1333	12	1296	18	1296	18	2.854938272
15AP27_94.FIN2	91.4	1.886	2.649	0.047	0.2246	0.0032	0.46379	1313	13	1306	17	1332	36	1332	36	1.951951952
15AP27_52.FIN2	120.1	1.053	2.63	0.11	0.2227	0.007	0.58141	1308	29	1295	37	1366	64	1366	64	5.197657394
15AP27_86.FIN2	172.3	3.17	2.479	0.059	0.2017	0.0059	0.6364	1262	17	1183	32	1444	44	1444	44	18.07479224
15AP27_58.FIN2	64.9	1.055	3.342	0.058	0.2626	0.0032	0.42966	1490	13	1502	16	1500	27	1500	27	0.133333333
15AP27_104.FIN2	316	2.45	3.655	0.032	0.2784	0.0022	0.60407	1561	7	1583	11	1531	14	1531	14	3.396472894
15AP27_71.FIN2	235.3	1.415	3.537	0.05	0.2687	0.0048	0.59476	1536	11	1534	24	1546	26	1546	26	0.776196636

15AP27_72.FIN2	549	21.8	3.856	0.039	0.2865	0.003	0.48012	1603.9	8.1	1626	15	1580	20	1580	20	2.911392405
15AP27_120.FIN2	63.4	1.236	3.7	0.082	0.2716	0.0058	0.53949	1571	17	1547	30	1631	38	1631	38	5.150214592
15AP27_107.FIN2	235	2.48	4.078	0.062	0.2924	0.004	0.69501	1648	12	1653	20	1635	28	1635	28	1.100917431
15AP27_96.FIN2	201	1.839	3.933	0.062	0.2844	0.0049	0.46911	1621	12	1613	24	1639	30	1639	30	1.58633313
15AP27_80.FIN2	140.2	0.858	4.134	0.061	0.2964	0.0048	0.57079	1662	12	1673	24	1650	29	1650	29	1.393939394
15AP27_45.FIN2	237.9	1.494	3.988	0.089	0.2804	0.0064	0.59652	1631	18	1592	32	1653	40	1653	40	3.690260133
15AP27_121.FIN2	46.7	0.791	3.8	0.16	0.268	0.01	0.85316	1585	34	1525	51	1670	41	1670	41	8.682634731
15AP27_64.FIN2	141.7	1.049	4.219	0.07	0.298	0.0039	0.588	1676	13	1680	19	1674	24	1674	24	0.358422939
15AP27_127.FIN2	37.1	0.569	4.102	0.087	0.2861	0.0049	0.32618	1652	17	1621	24	1701	42	1701	42	4.703115814
15AP27_1.FIN2	81.8	1.233	3.68	0.11	0.2547	0.0063	0.71735	1564	23	1461	32	1710	35	1710	35	14.56140351
15AP27_63.FIN2	79.5	1.135	4.567	0.074	0.3129	0.0042	0.34503	1741	13	1754	21	1737	31	1737	31	0.978698906
15AP27_24.FIN2	271.4	2.048	4.54	0.12	0.3043	0.0081	0.79896	1732	21	1710	40	1748	34	1748	34	2.173913043
15AP27_116.FIN2	65.8	1.118	4.606	0.09	0.3086	0.0053	0.49735	1751	16	1736	27	1754	34	1754	34	1.02622577
15AP27_102.FIN2	217	2.883	4.766	0.067	0.3196	0.0043	0.56465	1779	12	1792	21	1764	20	1764	20	1.587301587
15AP27_103.FIN2	342	7.44	4.706	0.049	0.3116	0.003	0.65257	1767.4	8.8	1748	15	1793	16	1793	16	2.509760178
15AP27_65.FIN2	302.1	1.692	5.01	0.1	0.3228	0.0073	0.65262	1817	17	1806	35	1832	31	1832	31	1.419213974
15AP27_37.FIN2	195.1	0.87	4.862	0.077	0.3114	0.005	0.65859	1793	13	1749	24	1835	24	1835	24	4.686648501
15AP27_98.FIN2	42.1	2.42	5.14	0.1	0.3231	0.0049	0.29233	1841	17	1804	24	1858	39	1858	39	2.906350915
15AP27_101.FIN2	358	2.659	4.97	0.11	0.3209	0.0077	0.62163	1817	19	1792	38	1861	37	1861	37	3.707684041
15AP27_114.FIN2	76.9	0.49	5.621	0.064	0.3485	0.0033	0.50516	1917.8	9.9	1927	16	1900	20	1900	20	1.421052632
15AP27_105.FIN2	233.9	1.637	5.888	0.067	0.3568	0.0038	0.66484	1958	10	1966	18	1962	16	1962	16	0.203873598
15AP27_35.FIN2	181.5	0.8351	5.497	0.076	0.321	0.004	0.58135	1902	11	1794	20	2001	22	2001	22	10.34482759
15AP27_75.FIN2	617.5	2.093	6.375	0.085	0.36	0.0045	0.52906	2029	12	1981	21	2069	21	2069	21	4.253262446
15AP27_13.FIN2	85.8	1.606	5.93	0.18	0.33	0.014	0.63514	1959	26	1840	66	2090	51	2090	51	11.96172249
15AP27_25.FIN2	76.3	1.468	7.27	0.2	0.369	0.013	0.67394	2142	25	2027	60	2235	40	2235	40	9.306487696
15AP27_19.FIN2	187.2	4.86	9.14	0.34	0.434	0.013	0.68048	2357	33	2319	60	2365	45	2365	45	1.945031712
15AP27_21.FIN2	95.6	2.03	9.51	0.24	0.414	0.011	0.60559	2385	23	2225	50	2489	37	2489	37	10.60666935
15AP27_97.FIN2	15.41	0.758	11.48	0.23	0.4912	0.0079	0.26401	2556	18	2578	34	2552	32	2552	32	1.018808777
15AP27_84.FIN2	612	2.323	10.79	0.19	0.4552	0.007	0.68946	2511	15	2421	32	2587	20	2587	20	6.416698879
15AP27_5.FIN2	155.7	2.378	13.38	0.17	0.4996	0.0074	0.56815	2705	12	2610	32	2774	22	2774	22	5.912040375